

Spectral unmixing and machine learning techniques for Co- Ni-Cu exploration in Aramo (Spain)

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Resumo

Esta tese de mestrado foi desenvolvida no contexto de um projeto pertencente ao “Horizon Europe” da União Europeia (UE) denominado Secure Sustainable Supply of Raw Materials for EU Industry (S34I). O S34I explorou o potencial de diferentes locais piloto no desenvolvimento e teste de métodos ligados à Observação da Terra (EO). Esta dissertação foca-se na Sierra del Aramo (Asturias, Spain), um local privilegiado para testar técnicas para mapear mineralização de matérias-primas críticas (CRM), devido ao seu histórico ligado à mineração, à sua relativamente baixa cobertura vegetal e também ao interesse da EU por estes materiais.

O trabalho aqui apresentado foca-se em dois temas principais: em primeiro lugar, desenvolver e testar técnicas de desmistura espectral como forma de identificar ocorrências relacionadas com a mineralogia local, baseadas na sua assinatura espectral. A segunda componente é centrada em testar múltiplos algoritmos de inteligência artificial (AI), na categoria de aprendizagem da máquina (ML), como forma de integrar múltiplos conjuntos de dados geológicos e realizar mapeamento de prospectividade mineral (MPM).

Para processar dados hiperespectrais, o trabalho começou por explorar o estado da arte de software para aplicações de deteção remota na geologia. Com o tempo, o trabalho evoluiu para uma abordagem mais flexível e personalizável que explora técnicas como redução de dimensionalidade, análise de elementos e desmistura espectral como forma de obter informação relacionada com a mineralização local.

Na segunda componente desta dissertação, o objetivo foi desenvolver um conjunto de ferramentas para a exploração mineral. Para alcançar esta tarefa, foram testados vários algoritmos, nomeadamente, Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest (RF), XGBoost, CatBoost e Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), com o objetivo de testar a sua capacidade de reconhecer padrões em um total de 37 conjuntos de dados de entrada e realizar MPM. O modelo com melhor desempenho, um empate técnico entre RF e XGBoost, alcançou uma precisão média de 0,92. Os modelos também avaliam a importância que os diferentes conjuntos de dados de entrada têm na previsão, podendo fornecer um entendimento mais profundo da mineralização local.

Keywords: Deteção Remota, Prospeção Mineral, Geologia Aplicada, Desmistura Espectral, Integração de dados, Matérias Primas Críticas, Deteção de alvos, Diferenciação de Carbonatos

Abstract

This Master's thesis was developed in the context of a European Union (EU) Horizon Europe project named Secure Sustainable Supply of Raw Materials for EU Industry (S34I). S34I explored the potential of six different pilot sites for developing and testing Earth Observation (EO) data/techniques. This dissertation focuses on Sierra del Aramo (Asturias, Spain), a prime location for testing techniques to map critical raw materials (CRM) mineralizations due to its legacy in extraction, relatively low vegetation coverage, and renewed interest from the EU in such materials.

The work presented here centers around two main topics: first, the development and testing of spectral unmixing techniques to identify features related to the region's mineralogical characteristics based on their spectral signature. The second component focused on testing multiple artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms in the category of machine learning (ML) as a means of integrating multiple datasets containing geological data to perform mineral prospectivity mapping (MPM).

To process hyperspectral data, the work began by exploring state-of-the-art software for remote sensing applications in geology. Over time, the workflow transitioned toward a more flexible and customizable approach, exploring techniques such as dimensionality reduction, endmember extraction, spectral unmixing, and minimum wavelength mapping as a means of retrieving information related to the local mineralization.

In the second component of this thesis, the goal was to develop a set of tools for mineral exploration. To achieve this task, multiple algorithms, namely Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest (RF), XGBoost, CatBoost, and a Multilayer Perceptron, were tested as a way of recognizing patterns in a total of 37 input datasets, successfully allowing MPM. The model with the best performance, a tie between Random Forest and XGBoost, achieved an average precision of 0.92. The models also evaluate the significance that different input variables have in the model prediction, potentially providing a deeper understanding of the local mineralization.

Keywords: Remote Sensing, Mineral Exploration, Applied Geology, Spectral Unmixing, Data Integration, Critical Raw Materials, Target Detection, Carbonate Differentiation

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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
ASI	Italian Space Agency
AUC	Area Under the Curve
ALZ	Austurian-Leonese Zone
ASI	Italian Space Agency
BNNs	Bayesian Neural Networks
CatBoost	Categorical Boosting
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CO	Cobalt
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRM	Critical Raw Materials
Cu	Copper
CZ	Cantabrian Zone
DBSCAN	Density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise
DEMs	Digital Elevation Models
EMS	Electromagnetic Spectrum
EnMap	Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program
ENVI	Environment for Visualizing Images
EO	Earth Observation
EU	European Union
FN	False Negative
FP	False Positive
FPR	False Positive Rate
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
GMMs	Gaussian Mixture Models
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HSI	Hyperspectral Imaging
ICA	Independent Component Analysis
IEA	International Energy Agency
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LSU	Linear Spectral Unmixing

Mg	Magnesium
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
MNF	Minimum Noise Fraction
MPM	Mineral Prospectivity Mapping
MTMF	Mixture Tuned Matched Filtering
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
Ni	Nickel
nm	Nanometer
NMF	Non-negative Matrix Factorization
OPTICS	Ordering Points to Identify Cluster Structure
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PPI	Pixel Purity Index
PR	Precision-Recall
PRISMA	Precursore IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa
RF	Random Forest
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic
SAM	Spectral Angle Mapper
SMOTE	Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique
SOM	Self-organizing Map
SVM	Support Vector Machine
SWIR	Short-wave Infrared
S34I	Secure Sustainable Supply of Raw Materials for EU Industry
TN	True Negative
TP	True Positive
TPR	True Positive Rate
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UMAP	Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection
VNIR	Visible and near-infrared
VRAM	Video Random Access Memory
XGBoost	Extreme Gradient Boosting
μm	Micrometer

1. Introduction

The present work was carried out within the framework of a European Union (EU) Horizon Europe programme, specifically within a project named Secure Sustainable Supply of Raw Materials for the EU Industry (S34I), dedicated to research and innovation on data-driven methods applied to Earth Observation (EO) data.

S34I (<https://s34i.eu/>) developed novel data-driven methods for analyzing the Earth using sensors at all scales, from *in situ* to satellite scale, and providing crucial information for all stages of the mining lifecycle: exploration, extraction, and closure/post-closure. In this way, the project contributed to reducing Europe's dependency on external sources for critical raw materials (CRMs) and increasing domestic acceptance for mining by providing tools that can improve legislation and control at later stages of the mining cycle.

Aramo, located in Asturias, Spain, was the main pilot in the context of land exploration within S34I, with legacy mining of Cobalt (Co), Nickel (Ni), and Copper (Cu) in the region. It is also considered a prime place for developing EO methods for mineral exploration due to its relatively low vegetation coverage. The theme of this dissertation is “Spectral unmixing and machine learning techniques for Co-Ni-Cu exploration in Aramo (Spain)”, a relevant topic in a context where EU demand for CRMs is increasing.

Such demand for CRMs is increasing due to the technological transition associated with the usage of non-carbon-emitting technologies (IEA, 2021). According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), the green transition is associated with an increased demand for technologies such as batteries, electric vehicles, wind turbines, and solar panels. It's currently expected that the demand for CRMs will increase by a magnitude of three times by the year 2040 (IEA, 2021).

With new sensors with improved characteristics, the size of the datasets is also increasing. This factor, alongside advancements in technology in general, has led to an increase in the use of algorithms related to Machine Learning (ML) to aid in data analysis, a recent academic topic that has been gaining exponential attention (Shirmard et al., 2022). On this topic, the development of predictive maps can be accomplished by making correlations between input data, such as characteristics normally associated with mineral occurrences and potential for the presence of mineral deposits (output), since those algorithms are efficient at recognizing subtle, complex, and non-linear relationships between spatial signatures (Yin & Li, 2022).

The main dataset explored throughout this dissertation is a hyperspectral image provided by the Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program (EnMap). Fundamentally, a hyperspectral image is an image where the response between light and a given material is recorded in fine detail across multiple contiguous bands, providing more detail to the material's response than a normal image. Some additional datasets related to regional geological characteristics, such as lithology, geological contacts, and faults/thrusts, were also generated in later stages since these features are closely related to the mineralization processes.

Therefore, this work can be divided into two main phases: (I) the development and testing of spectral unmixing techniques, aiming to identify variations in regional mineralogical characteristics based on their diagnostic spectral signatures (Figure 1). (II) Implementing and testing multiple ML models as a means for integrating multiple datasets containing geological data, therefore understanding patterns related to the mineralization, and enabling Mineral Prospectivity Mapping (MPM).

Figure 1. Use of hyperspectral data for material characterization in geological applications. a) Almandine mineral. b) Respective infrared spectrum. (Santos et al., 2025)

In the first phase, the complexity of satellite hyperspectral data was explored to acquire datasets related to the distribution of materials that occur in the region, potentially providing insights into the mineralization system present. Multiple steps are needed to properly extract information from hyperspectral datasets; those will be discussed in the later stages of this work, as well as the potential for automating steps and improving final results in the future. Multiple techniques, such as dimensionality reduction algorithms, endmember extraction, spectral unmixing techniques, and minimum wavelength mapping, were tested and allowed for the generation of new datasets, which were crucial for MPM.

In recent years, different ML algorithms have been developed for pattern recognition and big data analysis. The second component of this thesis focuses on testing multiple ML algorithms, namely, Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost, Chen & Guestrin, 2016), Random Forest (RF, Breiman, 2001), Categorical Boosting (CatBoost, Prokhorenkova et al., 2019), Support Vector Machines (SVM, Cortes & Vapnik, 1995) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) in the form of a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP, Werbos, 1982). While leveraging these algorithms, the objective is to explore their characteristics while aiming to achieve MPM based on understanding patterns between data in multiple datasets. In the second phase, the datasets generated in the first phase were used, as well as other geological datasets (such as faults and lithology) and maps developed and provided by S34I project partners studying the Aramo region.

While many ML and Deep Learning (DL) models have been applied to perform MPM, there is not a single algorithm that consistently outperforms others across different study regions, input dataset types, performance metrics, and class imbalances in training data. For instance, RF has shown great performance across multiple studies, while other authors recognize the capacity for Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) to outperform in recognition of spatial patterns (Lou & Liu, 2023; Sun et al., 2020), those capabilities for recognizing spatial patterns are strongly related to the nature of CNN's since the dataset is processed as an image instead of each pixel being considered as a spatially independent row of data.

Therefore, the normal process is to evaluate each algorithm's strengths and weaknesses and make a decision, ideally to enhance the effectiveness, speed, and reliability of the analysis. The algorithms chosen for this work developed similar final products, but with small differences that have potential implications for future use case scenarios. During this work, their implementation, results, and potential advantages and/or implications for future applications will be discussed in the respective chapters.

To manage all the data in a reliable, interpretable way that emphasizes the physical meaning of the datasets being studied, the use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) is mandatory due to the effectiveness of these systems in allowing the user to interact and analyze spatial data (Beato et al., 2019).

At the start of this thesis, to process the hyperspectral data, Environment for Visualizing Images (ENVI) software (NV5 Geospatial v5.6, 2025) was explored, used both as a means for learning and to explore the first preliminary results. Over time, the work transitioned into developing application-specific functions, which were developed in Python language (Van Rossum & Drake, 2009).

While understanding the lack of freely open-source software (Prokakis, 2022), especially for spectral unmixing independently of proprietary packages. An alternative software was developed featuring an intuitive graphical user interface (GUI) and providing access to all the functions developed and used. AetherGeo (Santos et al., 2025) spectral analysis capabilities were the core component of the hyperspectral data analysis done throughout this dissertation.

These advancements, in conjunction with easier and more reliable ways to acquire data, are leading towards more cost-effective ways for geologists to work on exploration. This is a crucial step for the EU to achieve the objectives defined for the following years.

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1.1 Geographic Setting

The area being studied in this work, Aramo, is located in Asturias, north of Spain. This area (Figure 2) encompasses the Saint Patrick Exploration License (Table 1), under Technology Minerals Plc (<https://www.technologyminerals.co.uk/>), registered with permit number 30858, focusing on the exploration of Co, Cu, and Ni.

The Sierra del Aramo is a plateau with topographic heights ranging from approximately 600 to 1791 meters above sea level (Figure 3). Many factors contribute to the area's lesser vegetation cover, making it an ideal test target for remote sensing studies. The local mineralization has been explored for a long time. They also have immense archaeological interest, since they were explored from around 1700 to 1000 BC. (Dory & Villers, 1893), returning to exploration in 1888 and labouring until the end of the 60s decade (Sánchez, 2020).

The Texeo or Aramo Mine site is about 27 km from Oviedo, the capital of Asturias. The mine is located on the eastern side of Sierra del Aramo and separates the basins of Mieres y Riosa on the east side and Quirós on the western side.

Figure 2. St. Patrick License (Archibald, 2021).

Table 1. St. Patrick License Corner Points (Archibald, 2021).

NODE	LONGITUDE	LATITUDE
PP	6°00'00"W	43°15'00"N
1	5°56'20"W	43°15'00"N
2	5°56'20"W	43°13'60"N
3	5°55'60"W	43°13'60"N
4	5°55'60"W	43°13'40"N
5	5°55'40"W	43°13'40"N
6	5°55'40"W	43°13'20"N
7	5°55'20"W	43°13'20"N
8	5°55'20"W	43°13'00"N
9	5°55'00"W	43°13'00"N
10	5°55'00"W	43°12'40"N
11	5°54'40"W	43°12'40"N
12	5°54'40"W	43°12'20"N
13	5°54'00"W	43°12'20"N
14	5°54'00"W	43°11'40"N

NODE	LONGITUDE	LATITUDE
15	5°53'40"W	43°11'40"N
16	5°53'40"W	43°10'60"N
17	5°54'00"W	43°10'60"N
18	5°54'00"W	43°10'00"N
19	5°53'40"W	43°10'00"N
20	5°53'40"W	43°09'40"N
21	5°54'40"W	43°09'40"N
22	5°54'40"W	43v10'00"N
23	5°55'60"W	43°10'00"N
24	5°55'60"W	43°10'20"N
25	5°56'40"W	43°10'20"N
26	5°56'40"W	43°10'00"N
27	5°58'00"W	43°10'00"N
28	5°58'00"W	43°10'40"N
29	5°58'20"W	43°10'40"N

NODE	LONGITUDE	LATITUDE
30	5°58'20"W	43°10'60"N
31	5°58'40"W	43°10'60"N
32	5°58'40"W	43°12'00"N
33	5°59'40"W	43°12'00"N
34	5°59'40"W	43°12'20"N
35	6°00'20"W	43°12'20"N
36	6°00'20"W	43v13'00"N
37	5°59'20"W	43°13'00"N
38	5°59'20"W	43°13'40"N
39	6°00'20"W	43°13'40"N
40	6°00'20"W	43°14'40"N
41	6°00'00"W	43°14'40"N
PP	6°00'00"W	43°15'00"N

Figure 3. Sierra del Aramo (Bergua et al., 2019).

1.2 Main work tasks

The current work mainly revolves around developing and testing recent or even new tools to enhance the detection of mineralization through data analysis and integration.

To achieve the desired outcome, three main components need to coexist:

- **Data acquisition and management:** Collecting, organizing, and visualizing various initial datasets (for example, the regional geological map and hyperspectral images) while ensuring their accurate geospatial alignment by leveraging GIS software properties, namely using QGIS.
- **Data preprocessing and analysis:** Retrieving information and generating new datasets that may correlate with the local mineralization from those initial datasets. This process can be based on extracting information from vector files (for example, geological faults) or, for example, applying data analysis techniques to hyperspectral data to retrieve datasets with more specific meanings.
- **Data integration:** The final component involves utilizing all the retrieved datasets and building a final integration workflow to employ MPM in the study region. This process also yields two distinct outcomes: first, a model evaluation to assess predictive performance; and second, an analysis of the contribution of each initial dataset to the final prediction, providing potential insights into the local mineralizations.

Data acquisition and management

In this component, the use of GIS is essential, leading to visual ways of interacting with data, especially in the context where the representation of its spatial components is crucial. GIS software applications constitute robust systems that store and manage a wide range of data (Beato et al., 2019). Understanding spatial relationships in the data is essential for achieving a deeper awareness of the geological phenomena associated with the occurrence of mineral concentrations of economic interest, and therefore, it is an essential task when the final objective is to detect such occurrences.

For data integration to properly work, data must be well structured and represent what we are trying to describe in the most reliable and representative way possible. This step means taking into consideration any detail that could lead to future errors (such as small

geospatial distortions associated with transforming data from distinct coordinate systems). Understanding this component is essential for structuring the work plans; otherwise, the predictive maps will not represent the intended outcome properly.

Data preprocessing and analysis

Multiple datasets are proposed for integration in the final results, involving characteristics that undermine geological features, such as structural and remote sensing endmember abundance maps. For the context of this work, the main acquisition of new datasets is centred around hyperspectral remote sensing, especially using spectral unmixing to identify the distribution of the different materials that occur in the study region. Endmember extraction techniques allow for a deeper understanding of the different materials in a given image; in this case, the term endmember is used to denote the different spectral signals present in the hyperspectral image, the objective is to understand which materials are associated with such spectral characteristics. The opposite is also possible, which means using a known spectra and evaluating the presence of such characteristic signature in an image.

Applying spectral unmixing techniques to an image aims to enable the user to understand or associate the presence of a given material with certain pixels in the image based on the characteristics of the material spectra and the spectra associated with a given pixel. Differencing between classifying a pixel based on the presence or non-presence of a given material is a different task than mapping the abundance of such given material within that area (pixel), although the analysis of unmixing results can be performed in either direction based on the specific algorithm used and the confidence in the results.

Either way, when performing these analyses using endmembers derived from using endmember extraction algorithms, these techniques allow for identifying different materials without requiring previous information or field trips, while also being adjusted by default to the characteristics of the sensor acquiring the data. The spectra associated with such endmembers can later be compared with spectra measured in laboratory conditions (Keshava & Mustard, 2002).

Data integration

The implementation of cutting-edge artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms, either in the fields of ML or DL, is possible due to advancements in computing power and data management (Jordan & Mitchell, 2015). The primary objective of this component is to employ an AI-driven approach that incorporates geological and remote sensing data to predict mineralogical occurrences and provide insights into the relative influence of input datasets on the prediction.

Understanding and pre-processing the input layers to develop predictive maps is crucial. This requires the user to evaluate how each layer relates to the other and the variable it represents. For example, the creation of buffers around faults in a structural data layer is important for allowing the algorithm to evaluate the relationship between the presence of faults and their influence on the likelihood of nearby zones containing potential alteration and/or mineralization (Liu et al., 2023), but also requires expert knowledge to decide the buffer distance.

On this topic, it is crucial to understand that for some models, an increase in input datasets or variables does not directly correlate with better results, leading to an increase in complexity and potentially more errors. In the case of Figure 4, RF was the algorithm of choice to develop two predictivity maps; the first one was created from 35 input maps, and after this process, a second map was generated using only the 10 datasets considered by the algorithm to be the most significant for the generation of the first map (Harris et al., 2022a). The results are very similar in both maps.

Figure 4. Au predictivity maps (Harris et al., 2022a) based on a) 35 predictor maps; b) 10 predictor maps.

1.3 State of the Art

The methodologies developed and tested in this work aim to generate predictive maps for mineralizations in the Aramo region (Spain), specifically in Sierra del Aramo. The geologic map of the region can be seen in Attachment A (Pello, 1973). The plateau is represented in the lower central-east part of the 1:50,000 (Attachment A, Figure 69) map, and is composed of dolomites, limestones, sandstones, shales, microconglomerate, and siltstones.

The region has a history of extraction for Co, Ni, and Cu source minerals, with even possible contamination problems associated with leftover stockpiles from mining and metallurgical processes (Loredo et al., 2008). According to *Paniagua et al. (1988)*, the mineralizations are mainly composed of Cu-Co-Ni arsenides and sulfides that occur in association with dolomite, quartz, and later calcite, and are hosted within a predominantly limestone sequence of Upper Carboniferous age (Tournaisian-Namurian).

The mineral assemblages have three primary stages, followed by a supergene stage associated with the weathering processes on the upper part of the ore deposit (Archibald, 2021; Loredo et al., 1988). Important structural and morphological features (such as faults, thrusts, or even height variation over time) can be associated with the mineral deposit; such information is important to take into consideration when choosing the right datasets to integrate and achieve predictive maps.

Mahboob et al. (2024) described two main requirements for achieving predictive maps: the use of different input datasets and their integration. The predictive maps highlighted in Figure 5 were built using different maps (but with common patterns) using the same input datasets and training data. Those algorithms used for integration are: SVM, RF, and CNN. As for the input datasets, the following are referred (Mahboob et al., 2024):

Figure 5. Predictive maps for Cu Prospectivity based on different ML algorithms (Mahboob et al., 2024).

- A geologic map of the region;
- Proximity of local mineralizations to intrusive contacts;
- Spatial proximity to geological features (lineaments and faults);
- Elevation and Slope maps;
- Iron-Oxide, Argillic, Phyllic and Propylitic alteration maps (performed using remote sensing, mainly focused on band ratios already established in the literature).

Since the analysis of satellite hyperspectral data is a core component of this dissertation, it is important to highlight the close relationship between absorption features and the main constituent of the local base geology (composed mostly of carbonate rocks).

Carbonate minerals have characteristic absorption features due to the harmonic and combinational bands in the C-O bond of the CO_3^{2-} in the reflective region of the electromagnetic spectrum (EMS, Gupta, 2018). In case of $CaCO_3$ the main absorption features seem to be around the 1.87, 1.99, 2.12, and 2.33 μm . In the case of dolomite, as magnesium (Mg) increases in the chemical composition there is a tendency for the absorption features to be centred around slightly shorter wavelengths. While this makes it technically possible to distinguish such variations, the spectral shift is minimal; therefore, high spectral resolution data is required to map these changes effectively.

Figure 6 highlights endmembers (“pure spectra”) obtained with very high spatial and spectral resolution data, assessing the variation in the main absorption band for carbonates when the relative percentage of calcite to dolomite changes (Krupnik & Khan, 2020). In this way, it highlights the capabilities of hyperspectral data to differentiate

carbonates but also shows the dependence on spectral resolution to achieve such a task.

Following the work of *Van der Meer (1995)*, it has been well established that measuring the absolute position of the characteristic carbonate absorptions in the short-wave infrared (SWIR) region makes it possible to measure the degree of dolomitization. This is achieved by observing that a shift to shorter wavelengths directly correlates with the dolomite-calcite ratio. The main limitation of this approach is that, although its effectiveness has been demonstrated in laboratory conditions, few studies have focused on mapping the variation of such carbonate minerals using only satellite data.

Figure 6. Variations in the carbonate absorption feature according to Calcite-Dolomite composition changes (Krupnik and Khan., 2020).

As this dissertation focuses on including multiple datasets to perform MPM, it leverages multiple datasets that have been processed in the context of S34I for the region of study. The latter part of this subsection provides a brief overview of such datasets and their key individual findings.

Cardoso-Fernandes et al. (2023), in the context of the S34i project, tested visualizing multiple combinations of different spectral bands by transforming them into RGB images, while also testing other methods such as Band Ratios, Dimensionality Reduction techniques, and Unsupervised Learning Clustering algorithms. The results prove the capabilities of different remote sensing data analysis techniques to differentiate characteristics at the regional and local level (Figure 7), even with medium spatial and low spectral resolution images (the original image is from the Landsat-8 satellite).

Figure 7. Unsupervised Clustering (k-means) results for Sentinel-2 image (Cardoso-Fernandes et al., 2023). a) 14 clusters, and B2, B3, B4, B5, B6, B7, B8, B11 and B12 as inputs. b) 8 clusters and B2, B3, B4, B5, B6, B7, B8, B11 and B12 as inputs. c) 14 clusters and B2, B3, B4, B8, B11, B12 as inputs. D) 8 clusters and B2, B3, B4, B8, B11 and B12 as inputs.

For supervised classification attempts, *Carvalho et al. (2024)* had good results applying ensemble algorithms, namely, XGBoost and RF. Since these algorithms require training data, the option was to use alteration zones that were previously identified during active exploration by Aurum Global Exploration. These zones, already identified as altered, served as labelled data for training the models and validating their results. This study highlighted the capabilities of using ML models to map alteration zones in the Aramo

region using multispectral and hyperspectral data from satellite sensors as the only input for the models. Having this information is important due to the close relationship between alteration zones and the local mineralization.

Figure 8 also compares the results for images from two distinct satellites, namely Landsat-9 and Precursore IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa (PRISMA). In terms of metrics, they performed well, despite the potential for false positives, which necessitated field validation (Carvalho et al., 2024). Another discussed topic is the possibility of overfitting in the case of PRISMA data, which is not common for Ensemble Boosting algorithms.

Figure 8. Alteration maps for Landsat-9 and Prisma Satellites. a) RF and Landsat-9 data; b) XGBoost and Landsat-9 data; c). RF and PRISMA data; XGBoost and PRISMA data Datum: WGS84, UTM Zone 30, scale 1: 150 000 (Carvalho et al., 2024).

Due to the strong regional structural deformations associated with the mineralization (Loredo et al., 1988), an important feature to take into account for the predictive models is data related to local faults and lineaments. Datasets from local geologic maps (Pello, 1973) can be used to obtain such data. However, more recent advancements allow for lineament extractions, automatic or manual, using satellite data (Araújo et al., 2024; Santos et al., 2023).

Due to the inherent characteristics of the carbonate rocks that compose the most representative lithological units in the area, and the epigenetic alteration associated with the mineralizations, the presence of different geomorphological features is common (Beato et al., 2019).

Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) is a techniques that enable the acquisition of very high resolution surface models from which it's possible to create Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) with high spatial resolution. Subsequently, when comparing two maps from different years, it is possible to evaluate the variation in terrain height between both dates (Azzalini et al., 2024). Figure 9 shows the results, especially highlighting zones of higher vertical displacement between 2012 and 2023.

As described before, the region's dominant lithologies are mainly composed of carbonate minerals, which are particularly reactive to chemical weathering. A possible association between zones with more vertical displacement and zones of alteration is an interesting feature to integrate into base datasets for MPM, and the results could provide insights into validating this hypothesis.

De La Rosa et al. (2025) explored airborne hyperspectral data for mapping the mineralization in the same region of this study, achieving good results (Figure 10). While airborne data provides more detailed information, especially in spatial resolution, the main drawback is the complex management and preprocessing of these extensive datasets requiring more computing power, and the costs associated with acquiring such data limit its application. Weather factors can also negatively affect the final outcome, besides limiting data acquisition (De La Rosa et al., 2025).

It is also important to note that throughout this dissertation, most of the hyperspectral image analysis was done with custom functions developed in Python (Van Rossum & Drake, 2009).

Figure 9. a) Displacement between 2012-2021 (m); b) Displacement between 2012-2023 (m); c) Points of match between datasets (m); d) Slope map (Degrees). (Azzalini et al., 2024)

Figure 10. Prospectivity map for the Aramo region using Bayesian Neural Networks (BNNs). (De La Rosa et al., 2025)

2. Geologic setting

2.1 Regional Geologic setting

According to Figure 11, the Aramo Plateau is close to the border between the Cantabrian Zone (CZ) and the Western Asturian-Leonese Zone (ALZ). The main characteristics of these zones are the following (Simancas et al., 2013):

Cantabrian Zone:

- Pre-orogenic sediments until the Lower Carboniferous;
- Syn-Orogenic sediments during the Upper Carboniferous;
- Thin-skinned, East-Vergent Orogenic deformation;
- Weak strain and no metamorphism.

Western Asturian-Leonese Zone:

- A much thicker Lower Palaeozoic sequence;
- East side deformation is overturned into recumbent folds and thrusts;
- A detachment level that is deeper than the Cantabrian Zone;
- Pervasive strain and metamorphism, with granites appearing at the boundary with the Central Iberian Zone.

Figure 11. Tectonostratigraphic zones and general cross-sections of the Iberian Variscides (Simancas et al., 2013). The red dot indicates the Aramo Region.

Appendix B contains a detailed map with cross-sections across the ESCI-N1 profile and the ALZ and CZ, highlighting the regional structure, especially related to the series of W-E trending fault systems. This region falls outside of the belts with extensive installation of granites and granitoids during the later phases of the Variscan orogeny, as identified in Figure 12 and classified inside zone I.

The deposits containing Cu in the Asturias region have been classified into two types (Álvarez et al., 2018):

- Skarns – Au-Cu deposits in the western part of the region with Cu sulphides and native Cu associated with gold
- Epithermal deposits – Ore bodies linked to accumulations associated with fractures and karst cavities, with a tendency to be displaced in irregular bodies and hosted in Carboniferous Limestones. These deposits exhibit an extraordinary variety of mineral species due to the intense processes of supergene alteration. This is the case for the Co-Ni-Cu deposit in Aramo.

Figure 12. Zones of Carboniferous magmatism in the Iberian Variscides (Simancas et al., 2013). The green dot indicates the Aramo Region.

2.2 Local Geologic setting

In the Cantabrian Zone, it is common for the occurrence of F, Ba, Co-Ni-Cu, As-Hg, and Pb-Zn mineral deposits close to late Variscan faults, indicating complex hydrothermal systems related to the geological events associated with the formation of those structures (Loredo & Garcia Iglesias, 1984).

Co-Ni-Cu deposits occur in limestones, especially near the Central Coal Basin. The mineralizations are strongly correlated with the previously discussed late Variscan faults (Paniagua et al., 1988), meaning that these faults are either previous or simultaneous to the mineralization installation processes.

As for the Aramo/Texteo mine, the mineralization, related to the Aramo Fault (Paniagua et al., 1988), falls under the epithermal deposit type and occurs in the allochthonous unit defined as Aramo Units, close to the contact with the Central Coal Basin (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Geologic Map associating the Fold and Nappe Province boundary with the Central Coal Basin, with detail for the Aramo Mine (Paniagua et al., 1988). 1) Lower Cambrian. 2) Middle Cambrian-Ordovician. 3) Silurian. 4) Devonian. 5) Tournaisian-Namurian. 6) Westphalian-Staphanian, A) normal contact. B) fault. C) thrust-fault. D) Co-Ni-Cu deposits.

As described before, those structural characteristics are intensely related to the mineralizations but also influence the region's morphology. The sandstones define more fragile areas that are later cut through by the fluvial network. The extensive network of fractures associated with the limestones gives rise to distinct morphological features. Additionally, periglacial processes that occur mainly in the higher areas, especially in the year's colder seasons, lead to zones of weakness where the dissolution of limestones intensifies, leading to accumulation deposits (Beato Bergua et al., 2018).

The mineral parageneses have been studied in detail. Table 2 (Archibald, 2021; Paniagua et al., 1988) highlights the different phases of mineralization and alteration.

Table 2. Paragenetic sequence in the Aramo mine (Archibald, S. M. 2021, adapted from Paniagua et al., 1988).

Minerals	Early Hydrothermal Stage	Intermediate Hydrothermal Stage	Late Hydrothermal Stage	Supergene Stage
Pyrite (FeS ₂)	█			
Bravoite (Fe,Ni,Co)S ₂	█			
Marcasite (FeS ₂)	█			
Cobaltite (CoAsS)	█			
Safflorite (Co,Fe)As ₂	█			
Sphalerite (ZnS)		█		
Acanthite (Ag ₂ S)		█		
Tennantite (Cu,Fe) ₁₂ As ₄ S ₁₃		█		
Chalcocopyrite (CuFeS ₂)			█	
Talnakhite (Cu ₉ (Fe, Ni) ₂ S ₁₆)			█	
S-rich bornite (Cu ₅ FeS ₄)			█	
Renierite(?) ((Cu, Zn) _n (Ge, As) ₂ Fe ₄ S ₁₆)			█	
Briartite(?) (Cu ₂ GeS ₄)			█	
Hex. Chalcocite (Cu ₂ S)			█	
Djurleite (Cu ₃ S ₆)			█	
Low Chalcocite (Cu ₂ S)			█	
Bornite (Cu ₅ FeS ₄)			█	
Blue Covellite (CuS)			█	
Normal Covellite (CuS)			█	
Digenite (Cu ₉ S ₂)				█
Native Silver (Ag)				█
Native Copper (Cu)				█
Cu-Co-Ni-Fe				█
Cu-Co-Ni oxides				█
Quartz	█	█	█	
Dolomite	█	█	█	
Calcite			█	█
Major Metals	Fe-Co-Ni-As	Zn-Cu-As	Cu-Fe	Cu-Fe-Ni-Co

According to Loredo et al. 1988, the later stage of supergene alteration led to a well-defined oxidation sequence, forming numerous Cu-S and Cu-Co minerals. As for the primary stages, fluid inclusion studies suggest a low-pressure and low-temperature epithermal-carbonate host model (Loredo & Garcia Iglesias, 1984).

The Co-Ni-Cu mineralization is mainly concentrated around E-W to NE-SW subvertical fault systems, with the primary mineralization closely related to the Aramo Fault (Archibald, 2021).

Archibald (2021) describes the ore as being primarily composed of Co-Ni-Cu sulfides, sulfoarsenides, hematite, and minor heavy metal selenides. The first stage encompasses the formation of pyrite and nickel-cobalt sulphides, with the transition to the second stage being marked by the formation of sphalerite (ZnS) and acanthite (Ag₂S). The last hydrothermal stage introduces the formation of minerals from the chalcopyrite group as well as Ni-Co sulphides, sulfoarsenides, selenides, and traces of native gold.

Based on Table 2, it is also possible to interpret that in the later stage, there is the formation of minerals such as Chalcocite, Bornite, Covellite, and Digenite, all being variations of copper sulphides, as well as native copper and silver due to the oxidative characteristics of the supergene process associated with this terminal phase.

It is also important to notice that the gangue material transitioned from mainly composed of dolomite and quartz to calcite in the last two stages.

Figure 14 refers to samples from underground veins and mine spoil samples collected during local interpretation by Aurum Mining (Archibald, 2021).

Sample AES33374: Level 4 St Pedro vein Dolomitised limestone network texture sulphides 0.5% Cu, 0.10% Ni & 0.33% Co

Sample AES33374: Level 4 St mine spoil mixed sulphides 31.2% Cu, 1.13% Ni & 0.42% Co

Figure 14. Mineral Samples from Aramo/Texteo Mine; A) Network textured sulphides, 0.5% Cu, 0.1% Ni, and 0.33% Co; B) Mixed sulphides, 31.2% Cu, 1.13% Ni, and 0.42% Co (Archibald., 2021).

Figure 15 shows the area around the Texeo/Aramo mine site, with around 40,000 m³ of waste from mine metallurgical operations. Meanwhile, the soils around the area also have high concentrations of metallic elements, surpassing the local background. Table 3 (Loredo et al., 2008) summarizes values for key elements. The problems associated with possible contaminations derived from water exposure to these accumulations have been described to a great extent in local studies (Ordóñez et al., 2005).

Figure 15. Location of mining works, spoil heaps and ruins of metallurgical plant. (Loredo et al., 2008)

Table 3. Concentrations for different elements measured in Waste materials and Soils around the Aramo Mine, values are in pmm (Loredo et al., 2008).

	Waste material	Soils
Cu	9,264	9,921
As	1,100	1,373
Co	549	685
Ni	840	1040

3. Machine learning and data integration

3.1 Machine learning

ML methods are powerful data-driven approaches for data analysis, and their importance is growing with the increase in the size and complexity of datasets. They excel at recognizing hidden patterns in input features. As discussed before, their reliability in analyzing spectral data is an important topic with promising results due to the robust characteristics of these algorithms against noise and uncertainties (Gewali et al., 2019). The capabilities of these algorithms can extend beyond spectral analysis, as they can be used to reduce high-dimensional data to lower dimensions, predict trends, and identify specific characteristics or components of the data. Leveraging these capabilities allows opportunities for improvement in decision-making and pattern recognition, even under complex scenarios (Cracknell & Reading, 2014).

As a brief introduction to this topic, it is important to know that ML algorithms can be categorized into five groups: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning, active learning, and transfer learning (Murphy, 2012).

Supervised learning involves recognizing patterns between input and output variables based on established labeled examples where output variable values are known (Hastie et al., 2009a). When working purely with unlabeled data, one possibility is using unsupervised learning algorithms since they separate the data into classes representing clusters of homogeneous characteristics (Hastie et al., 2009b).

Semi-supervised algorithms utilize both labeled and unlabeled data to understand the relationships between input and output variables. The main goal with semi-supervised learning is to achieve better results than training on labeled data alone (Zhu & Goldberg, 2009). In a somewhat similar context, active learning iteratively selects samples from the unlabeled data to be manually labelled, and incorporates them into the labeled set, repeating this process until the model achieves the desired performance. However, in most practical geological applications, acquiring extensive ground truth at the same pace as the algorithm would require for proper active learning is unfeasible, rendering the application of this chain of algorithms challenging or even unfeasible.

The last main branch of ML algorithms is transfer learning, where information learned from one problem is used to solve another problem. In this context, domain adaptation

is a subset of this area of study that aims to improve the understanding of the model in a given set of data and the capacity to solve a problem with a different dataset of the same nature (Pan & Yang, 2010).

A common problem in ML described in the literature is the bias and variance problem (Figure 16). Bias is the error associated with the model, which makes incorrect assumptions about the data. A practical example is using a linear model to determine data with nonlinear properties (Mehta et al., 2019). In the case of variance, it usually results from the model being too complex for the required task and/or amount of training data, meaning the model makes strong adjustments to small changes. High variance can be identified when the algorithm makes extensive changes to its predictions after a small increase in training data, indicating that the algorithm is memorizing the data instead of recognizing patterns (Figure 17).

Figure 16. Bias and Variance according to the relationship between Error and Number of training points (A) / Model Complexity (B) (adapted from Mehta et al. 2019).

In the context of very complex data, using a simple model tends to lead to underfitting, and the model cannot fully understand the complexity of the data. On the other hand, when the model has too many parameters for a simpler dataset, it tends to “memorize” the data instead of correctly estimating the tendencies (Aliferis & Simon, 2024).

In models that undergo a training process, it is important to evaluate the model's performance. To realize this task, it is necessary to separate the labeled data into isolated training and validation datasets since we want to understand the model's capabilities to learn instead of “memorizing” the data. For cases where a validation set is used for hyperparameter tuning, the set needs to be divided, keeping an independent set for unbiased performance evaluation (Gewali et al., 2019).

Figure 17. (A) Overfitting and (B) Underfitting (Adapted from Aliferes and Simon, 2024).

A confusion matrix is a simple way to display the results of a model, comparing the model's predictions with the ground truth data (Table 4). When evaluating the performance of a supervised learning model, several standard metrics that have already been established in the literature. Figure 18 highlights the standard metrics used for performance evaluation in binary classification.

Table 4. Confusion Matrix (Adapted from Cabot & Ross, 2023).

		Predicted	
		Positive	Negative
Ground Truth	Positive	True Positive (TP)	False Positive (FN)
	Negative	False Positive (FP)	True Negative (TN)

A receiver operating characteristic (ROC) is a graph commonly used to evaluate model performance (Figure 19). An ROC curve is displayed by plotting the False Positive Rate (FPR, calculated according to: $FPR = 1 - specificity$) on the X-axis and the True Positive Rate (TPR, also called sensitivity/recall) on the Y-axis (Sathyanarayanan & Roopashri Tantri, 2024). By calculating the Area Under the Curve (AUC), it is possible to retrieve a value between 0 and 1, where the maximum value means that the model is always correct in its predictions, and a value of 0.5 means that the model's predictions are no better than “flipping a coin” and random guessing the result (Cabot & Ross, 2023).

To complement the ROC AUC metric, especially in the case of unbalanced classes (for example, 70% of the data belonging to one class), it is common to include the Precision-

Recall (PR) curve; the AUC value for the PR curve is also called average precision (Figure 20). The main advantage is its adaptation to unbalanced classes (random guessing does not necessarily give an AUC value of 0.5) (Varoquaux & Colliot, 2023).

Box 1: Performance metrics for binary classification

Basic metrics
T denotes *test*: classifier output; *D* denotes *diseased* status.

- **Sensitivity (also called recall)**: fraction of positive samples actually retrieved.

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$$
- **Specificity**: fraction of negative samples actually classified as negative.

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN+FP}$$
- **Positive predictive value (PPV, also called precision)**: fraction of the positively classified samples which are indeed positive.

$$\text{PPV} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$$
- **Negative predictive value (NPV)**: fraction of the negatively classified samples which are indeed negative.

$$\text{NPV} = \frac{TN}{TN+FN}$$

Summary metrics

- **Accuracy**: fraction of the samples correctly classified.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+FP+TN+FN}$$
- **Balanced accuracy (BA)**: accuracy metric that accounts for unbalanced samples.

$$\text{BA} = \frac{\text{Sensitivity}+\text{Specificity}}{2}$$
- **F₁-score**: harmonic mean of PPV (precision) and sensitivity (recall).

$$F_1 = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{\text{PPV}} + \frac{1}{\text{Sensitivity}}} = \frac{2TP}{2TP+FP+FN}$$
- **Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC)**. MCC=1 for perfect classification, MCC=0 for random classification, MCC=-1 for perfectly wrong classification.

$$\text{MCC} = \frac{TP \times TN - FP \times FN}{\sqrt{(TP+FP) \times (TP+FN) \times (TN+FP) \times (TN+FN)}}$$
- **Markedness** = $\frac{TP}{TP+FP} - \frac{FP}{FP+TN} = \text{PPV} + \text{NPV} - 1$
- **Area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC AUC)**.
- **Area under the precision-recall curve (PR AUC, also called average precision)**.

Figure 18. Performance metrics for binary classification. Adapted from: (Varoquaux & Colliot, 2023).

Figure 19. ROC curve and AUC ROC scores for different classifiers (Varoquaux & Colliot, 2023).

Figure 20. Illustration of PR AUC classification metric (Aldrainli et al., 2020).

In the case of purely unlabeled data, a common approach involves organizing the data into distinct groups where similar components are grouped into classes, which is called clustering. The clustering algorithms described in this work are K-means, Iterative Self-Organizing Data Analysis Techniques (ISODATA), Ordering Points to Identify Cluster Structure (OPTICS), and Density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise (DBSCAN). Chapters 3.2.2 “Gaussian Mixture Models” and 3.2.4 “Density-Based Clustering” provide a more detailed explanation of their foundations.

The topic of clustering is considered an approach to data mining, an area that also includes regression, outlier analysis, classification, association, and prediction (Satapathy et al., 2019). Nowadays, datasets are getting more extensive and detailed; for this reason, the use of the algorithms that were just mentioned is increasing. These techniques are essential for this work due to their ability to understand patterns, leading to a deeper understanding of the data structure and enabling associations that are essential for the analysis developed.

3.2 Algorithms applied to data analysis

3.2.1 Support Vector Machines

SVMs, introduced by *Cortes and Vapnik (1995)*, are supervised learning models originally designed to perform binary classification by finding the optimal separating hyperplane between two classes. Since then, they have been applied in multiple geoscience fields due to their great capabilities in identifying subtle hidden patterns in data, even when the class boundaries are not obvious.

Figure 21 exemplifies the goal of SVMs by identifying a decision boundary while maximizing separation between classes. The decision boundary can either be linear or non-linear, depending on the kernel used for the separation hyperplane. By projecting the data into higher dimensions, the model can effectively fit a non-linear decision surface into the original linear decision hyperplane (Salcedo-Sanz et al., 2014). Another important concept for SVMs is the introduction of soft margins, which enables some misclassification on the analysis, essential for the algorithm to be robust against noise, while giving the model strong characteristics against overfitting (Cortes & Vapnik, 1995).

Figure 21. A) Plot with data from two classes that are not linearly separable. B) Linear SVM classification. C) Data projected to a higher dimension for class separability. D) Results of applying a non-linear kernel for class separation.

3.2.2 Distance-Based Clustering Models

Unsupervised distance-based clustering algorithms are often used for image classification, as they allow grouping of pixels with similar properties without requiring training data. Two of the most common approaches, and the ones explored during this dissertation, are K-Means (Arthur & Vassilvitskii, 2007) and ISODATA.

K-means (Arthur & Vassilvitskii, 2007) is an algorithm that interactively assigns each data point to the nearest cluster centroid (in the first iteration, the centroids can be random or pre-computed based on data properties), and iteratively updates the position of the centroids until the formed clusters stop changing significantly, also called convergence.

For the case of ISODATA, the fundamental concept is similar; however clusters can be joined or split during each interaction based on variance, meaning that the number of clusters can be dynamically updated (Narumalani et al., 2006; Rajyalakshmi et al., 2016).

Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs, Bilmes, 1998) are also a popular solution for unsupervised clustering. These statistical approaches model data distribution as a

weighted sum of Gaussian components. They have different applications due to being statistical models, rather than deterministic (as is the case for K-means and ISODATA). Another challenge for GMMs is the extra computational complexity, especially for large datasets such as hyperspectral images.

Figure 22. ISODATA Classification using cluster means (Rajyalakshmi et al., 2016).

3.2.3 Latent Linear Models

The most common latent linear models are Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (Wold et al., 1987) and Independent Component Analysis (ICA) (Comon, 1994). In the case of PCA, the data is linearly projected into a set of orthogonal axes while maximizing variance. The result is a set of components that maximize how uncorrelated each new component is to the other, while retaining as much of the original data as possible.

It is a similar process for ICA, but the orthogonality between axes is dropped. ICA aims to find statistically independent components by maximizing higher-order statistical measures (for example, kurtosis) (Comon, 1994). The difference between them can be better understood by interpreting Figure 23.

In essence, ICA is a method developed by the signal processing community that better adjusts to statistically independent components in the data. However, two assumptions must be made: the derived components need to be non-Gaussian and independent (Lee, 2008). Those requirements can affect how both are applied or their significance concerning the data.

Figure 23. a) Orthogonal axes PC1, PC2 in the case of PCA; b) Set of non-orthogonal axes in the application of ICA. (Based on Lee, 2008)

3.2.4 Density-based Clustering

Algorithms that are based on clustering points on the latent space by recognizing regions of higher density fall under a category named “Density-Based Clustering” (Figure 24). This approach also has the advantage of isolating very low-density regions that could, in some cases, represent noise in the data (Han et al., 2012).

In this dissertation, the only algorithm used from this category is OPTICS, introduced by *Ankerst et al. (1999)*, to solve one of the problems with DBSCAN, an algorithm introduced by the same team, but that does not work well with varying densities in the data. With the time complexity of $O(n \log n)$, the main advantage of OPTICS is that, when compared to other alternatives, it allows a higher degree of interpretation, requiring fewer parameters, which results in the person doing the analysis having an easier time interactively adjusting the parameters (Bhuyan & Borah, 2013).

Figure 24. Common Density-Based Clustering Algorithms (Scikit-Learn, 2025).

3.2.5 Artificial Neural Networks

ANN algorithms are biologically inspired computational models (Rumelhart et al., 1986) that, through more recent advancements in DL, have become highly capable of extracting hierarchical patterns and complex relationships from data (Schmidhuber, 2015). A core example is the MLP (Werbos, 1982), a feedforward architecture that consists of an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and a single output layer (Figure 25, Lancashire et al., 2009; Zafeiris et al., 2018). Training is done via a backpropagation algorithm adjusting internal weights in a way that minimizes error in the final output (Schmidhuber, 2015).

As an alternative, DL methods generally refer to algorithms that learn feature representations using multiple levels of abstractions, giving the model greater modelling power (Goodfellow et al., 2016), but requiring extensive datasets to be trained.

ANN-based algorithms for both ML and DL are continually being developed and progressively modified for applications in MPM since the algorithms show the ability to recognize complex patterns and aid in making intelligent decisions (Yousefi et al., 2021). These methods can be used across all types of learning, from supervised to unsupervised learning (Guo et al., 2016).

Figure 25. Example diagram for an artificial neural network algorithm (Zafeiris et al., 2018).

3.2.6 Ensemble learning

Ensemble learning is a supervised technique that merges results from multiple predictors with the aim of improving results. It provides interesting advantages, such as reduced risk, because even when the ensemble does not outperform every single classifier in terms of best performance, it reduces the risk of an unfortunate selection of a poorly performing classifier (Polikar, 2006).

There are some options to achieve this task. Perhaps the simplest to implement is bagging, where the data is divided into different subsets, and each classifier is trained on a given subset. After that, each classifier is merged by taking a majority vote for individual decisions (Breiman, 1996). This technique is advantageous when available data is limited because each subset can contain a large portion of the data (75% to 100%), with the same instances appearing in most subsets.

Boosting is another common term when referring to ensembles. Subsets of data are also created, and the final decision is based on majority voting (Figure 26), but the similarities to bagging end here, since the data is strategically divided into subsets to strategically provide each classifier the most informative training data for that given algorithm. This maximizes strong points for each of the individual classifiers (Schapire, 1990).

The last approach is stacking, which refers to algorithms that use multiple diverse models and learn how to best combine them into a meta-model.

Figure 26. Combining classifiers trained on different subsets of data (Polikar, 2006).

3.2.6.1 Random Forest

Random Forest is an ensemble classifier introduced by Brieman (2001), based on combining the predictions of multiple decision trees through majority voting (Khan et al., 2021). One of its advantages is that it can be effectively applied to different types of data, for example, binary, numerical, and categorical (Harris et al., 2022b).

It is a supervised classification algorithm, and so it requires training data. The two variable parameters are the number of variables associated with each tree and the

number of trees to create. Due to its structure, random forest is not prone to overfitting data, even when increasing the number of trees; it also works around noise in datasets (Harris et al., 2015).

Figure 27. Illustration of Random Forest Algorithm (Khan et al., 2021).

3.2.6.2 Extreme Gradient Boosting

XGBoost is a powerful and scalable implementation of gradient boosting, widely recognized for its state-of-the-art performance on tabular datasets containing numeric and/or categorical data. The model builds “trees” sequentially but explores gradient boosting as a means to minimize the prediction errors made by the previous “trees” (T. Chen & Guestrin, 2016).

3.2.6.3 Categorical Boosting

Catboost is an open-source gradient boosting library to build ensemble decision trees sequentially (Figure 28). Similar to XGBoost, it explores gradient boosting as a way of minimizing prediction error during training (Prokhorenkova et al., 2019). The algorithm is also improved in terms of not overfitting on training data due to a new approach to calculating leaf value when building the tree structure (Yao et al., 2021).

While being developed with the aim of working with categorical data, it also supports other types of inputs. The model also has native integration with multiple programming languages and has native implementation to run on central processing unit (CPU) and graphics processing unit (GPU) (Prokhorenkova et al., 2019).

Figure 28. Flow chart of the CatBoost algorithms (Yao et al., 2021).

4. Hyperspectral imaging

To understand hyperspectral imaging (HSI), it is essential to start by understanding how vision works. For example, humans have the capability to characterize three different zones in the EMS and therefore perceive color as a mixture of those components; an example can be seen in Figure 29 (Zhang et al., 2024).

Figure 29. Normalized spectral sensitivity of human retinal rod and cone cells (Zhang et al., 2024).

Sensors can capture more bands and broader regions of the EMS, and equipment that works based on material or element characterization based on the response to different zones of the EMS has been applied across multiple scales and various geological purposes (Bedini & Rasmussen, 2018; Fabre, 2020; Oyedotun, 2018). This work's primary focus will be centered around the visible and near-infrared (VNIR) and SWIR regions. New satellite hyperspectral missions provide data for those regions of the EMS, which will be described in greater detail in Chapter 5.2 "Remote Sensing".

For spectral data, two types are commonly described: multispectral and hyperspectral (Figure 30). The criterion for defining the difference is a discussion that is still going on in the literature. Still, for the most part, it can be agreed that multispectral means the

sensor acquires a relatively low number of bands, spaced unevenly across the EMS. Each band refers to a broader component of that same spectrum.

Meanwhile, in the case of hyperspectral sensors, the sensors can capture a larger number of bands, which are narrow (2-10 nm) and are usually spaced equally across the zone of the spectrum that is being measured (for example, increments of 10 nm per band) (Buddhiraju & Porwal, 2015; Kale et al., 2017).

Figure 30. Comparison of multispectral and hyperspectral imaging (Vines & Zhang, 2022).

Fundamentally, the recorded reflectance spectra vary based on the physical and chemical properties of the target material (Koerting et al., 2021). Those variations at a spectrum level can later be identified based on, for example, the presence of a specific absorption feature. Especially for the case of hyperspectral scanning sensors, the non-destructive properties and capability to differentiate minerals due to the high spectral resolution make this technique state-of-the-art for material characterization from the nanometric scale to the satellite scale (Daempfling et al., 2022; Schodlok et al., 2022).

4.1 Mineral differentiation with HSI

The most characteristic feature for distinguishing different minerals using HSI is the wavelength location of absorption feature minimums (Crowley et al., 1989). Still, other factors can be useful, such as symmetry of absorptions, which can differentiate mineral phases (van der Meer, 2004). Another factor is the intensity/magnitude of the absorption feature, something that has been correlated to higher concentrations of the mineral in question (Boesche et al., 2015) but also tends to increase with grain size (van der Meer, 1994).

Spectral mixtures are also a complex topic in HSI. Figure 31 highlights that even at a scale of 26 μm , it is rare to find a “pure pixel” composed of a single material (Portela et al., 2021).

Figure 31. Spectral mixtures at a microscopic scale (Portela et al., 2021).

Another exception is when a given mineral has no significant absorption feature, at least in the zone of the EMS measured. Opaque minerals have low overall reflectance, but an interesting feature is that their presence tends to diminish the spectral features of the other minerals present (Hunt, 1971; Krupnik & Khan, 2020).

4.1.1 The case of carbonate minerals

Carbonates have some absorption features in the 1600 to 2500 nm range, measuring up to seven different absorption bands in that zone of the spectrum (Van der Meer, 1995).

Dolomite, with the formula $CaMg(CO_3)_2$ crystallizes in the trigonal-rhombohedral system and exhibits an ordered alternation of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions along the crystal lattice. Magnesium substitution for calcium alters coordination environments ($Ca - O$ versus $Mg - O$ bond lengths), altering optical properties (McCormick et al., 2021).

In the case of calcite, the most intense feature tends to be situated at approximately 2330-2340 nm; this feature can be used to distinguish it from dolomite, due to the latter having an absorption feature of similar magnitude but that occurs at shorter wavelengths, approximately 2315-2320 nm according to Crowley (1986) or ~2320-2328 nm according to Pontual et al. (2008). By evaluating absorption band depth and minimum location placement, Krupnik & Kan (2020) concluded that mineral abundances and spectral characteristics were correlated (Figure 32). In this way, laboratory-based HSI could provide mineral estimates similar to point counting.

Figure 32. A) Mineral abundances obtained through point count in comparison to results from HSI mineral maps. B) Graph showing the correlations (Krupnik & Khan, 2020).

5. GIS and Remote Sensing

5.1 GIS

The use of well-established coordinate systems is critical to ensure proper spatial alignment; this is essential to ensure that when matching different data, the visualization matches the physical place it represents as well as possible (Longley et al., 2015). Also, the use of GIS has significantly improved data storage, indexing, and cartographic representations (Beato et al., 2019). In this way, it became a mandatory tool for analyzing, representing, and understanding the complex geologic environments surrounding the mineralized ore bodies.

Different methods can and should be used to acquire data, such as creating digital versions of existing maps, which may contain all data types, such as geographic, geological, topographic, and much more. When acquiring completely new data, sensors can obtain different types of data, such as optical, thermal, and synthetic aperture radar (SAR). After data processing, GIS allows the analysis and understanding of patterns in data and their spatial distribution. Especially when on board a satellite or aerial vehicle, due to the possibility of acquiring data for long extensions of terrain, an important feature for regional-scale geological studies, the acquired data can be used for different tasks such as interpretation of mineralogical patterns and structural mapping (Cardoso-Fernandes et al., 2020, 2022).

Advanced data analytics helps geologists overcome some of the problems associated with traditional methods, specifically concerning the subjective interpretation of data and the impact decision-making has on project spending. Another helpful benefit of digital methods is the ease of adjusting the study scale based on the project's exploration stage (Shirmard et al., 2022).

The development of ML models and their integration with GIS allows accurate predictions of potential mineralized areas. This enables exploration activities to focus on reduced, high-confidence areas, making mineral exploration faster, more cost-effective, and safer (Jooshaki et al., 2021).

5.2 Remote sensing

Mapping geological features is essential for anyone working on mineral exploration. ML methods and remote sensing data are considered relatively inexpensive approaches that show promising results in mapping alteration zones, indicator minerals for ore deposits, geological structures, and lithological units (Shirmard et al., 2022).

Leading to the topic of retrieving information from hyperspectral optical data (Chapter 6), this chapter will focus on optical data obtained from passive sensors, specifically on optical data. Despite recognising that other types of remote sensing data and related processed datasets can be used for integration, the specific pre-processing and analysis for those different types of data are outside the scope of this dissertation. Optical is usually used to describe the regions of EMS where the sun is used as the radiation source, while the term passive sensor is used to describe sensors that only capture radiation from external sources.

Figure 33 also provides important insights into variations in how the atmosphere absorbs different components of the EMS, which impacts noise or even forces the removal of bands that suffer from intensive absorption variations, even from slight changes in atmospheric composition/conditions.

Figure 33. The electromagnetic spectrum regions with additional information relative to passive and active sensors (Araújo, 2024; Prost, 2013).

While working with optical remote sensing data, it is interesting to understand that the observed spectrum would have the same shape as the spectrum of the respective material if the solar spectrum was flat and the atmosphere affected equally across all wavelengths, something that is unfortunately not true. To address this problem, some data pre-processing is necessary to transform an adimensional value into a

transmittance or reflectance (depending on the correction level), i.e., a variable with physical meaning. One of these steps is a correction considering the distortion associated with the impact of the atmosphere (Figure 34). For these reasons, efforts concerning measuring spectral properties of materials through the atmosphere must consider the atmospheric absorption zones (Figure 33). Sometimes, the signal-to-noise ratio is so low that those bands must to be removed for practical uses. For this reason, sophisticated atmospheric compensation codes are used to recover the spectrum for each image pixel, considering the sensor's distortions and characteristics (Manolakis et al., 2003).

Figure 34. Atmospheric effect on Sensor-measured radiance (Manolakis et al., 2003).

Although it is not the primary focus of this dissertation, another crucial pre-processing step is to apply denoising techniques (Yuan et al., 2012), as an essential feature of optic sensors is their signal-to-noise ratio, which varies across different wavelengths.

More recently, Cardoso-Fernandes et al. (2020) described the current research and future perspectives for the detection of lithium mineralization with sensors on spaceborne vehicles; in this work, the author describes different techniques, their applications and especially the advancements the study area has had in the last decades. Even though a lot has been done, there is still research and improvements to be made, and that can be

said for most of the problems, which are centered around balances between sensor spectral range, spectral and spatial resolution, and even added data complexity and size management as datasets get larger (Richards & Jia, 2006).

One of the problems is that today’s sensors have to sacrifice key characteristics, as explained below. Figure 35 shows where different sensors capture data across the EMS. Because of these differences, in the case of geologic studies, coverage of the SWIR region is of special importance for geologists as their sensitivity to rock and soil changes is essential to differentiate local characteristics (Shirmard et al., 2022).

As discussed previously, optical sensors fall into two distinct categories: multispectral and hyperspectral, based on the number of bands and whether they are contiguous across the part of the EMS being measured. For both cases, when an image is captured, for a given pixel in the image, there are three variables to consider: two of them are the coordinates, and the third is the bands, composed of multiple values associated with the reflectance values at different wavelengths (Figure 36).

Figure 35. Comparison between ASTER, Landsat 8, Sentinel-2 and WorldView-3 bands (Cardoso-Fernandes et al., 2020, adapted from USGS Landsat program, (2017)).

Figure 36. Hyperspectral data cube (Gewali et al., 2019).

Launched in November 2002 as part of the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) EO-1 Millennium Mission, the Hyperion sensor marked a significant milestone for HSI applications in remote sensing. Being the first hyperspectral sensor on board a spacecraft, providing data in the VNIR and SWIR wavelengths, with 242 spectral bands, ranging from 0.36 - 2.58 μm with a spatial resolution of 30 meters (Pearlman et al., 2003). Different minerals have been mapped using this sensor, such as calcite, dolomite, kaolinite, alunite, buddingtonite, muscovite, hydrothermal silica, and zeolites (Parashar et al., 2016).

Following up on free academic access satellite hyperspectral data, two main sensors are used: EnMap and PRISMA. The first one was recently launched in 2022 and includes a spectral range from 420 nm to 2450 nm with a spatial resolution of 30 m. Due to the nature of the satellite, it has a 30 km swath width and can acquire an image for the same target in just 4 days, when pointing feature is set for fast target revisit (German Aerospace Center, 2018).

Table 5 highlights some of the core characteristics of the EnMap sensor (German Aerospace Center, 2018). The data is available at product levels L1B (raw values are calibrated and geolocated), L1C (includes the previous and top-of-atmosphere

correction), and L2A (bottom of atmosphere correction and orthorectified) (German Aerospace Center, 2018).

Table 5. EnMap characteristics (German Aerospace Center, 2018).

Instrument Main Characteristics	
Swath / FOV	30km / 2.63°
Spectral range	420 nm – 2450 nm
Spectral sampling distance	6.5 nm (420 – 100nm) 10 nm (900 – 2450nm)
Spectral accuracy / stability	0.5 nm / 0.5 nm (VNIR) 1.0 nm / 0.5 nm (SWIR)
Signal-to-Noise ratio	> 500 (at 495 nm; VNIR) > 150 (at 2200 nm; SWIR)
Smile and keystone	< 0.2 pixel
Polarization sensitivity	< 5%
Radiometric resolution	> 14 bits
Radiometric accuracy / stability	5% / 2.5% (between two consecutive calibrations)

As for PRISMA, it was launched in 2018 by the Italian Space Agency (ASI). The spacecraft weighs approximately 830 kg and can capture images of the same location on Earth every 29 days. Table 6 (Adapted from Loizzo et al., 2018) highlights the sensor characteristics. Meanwhile, the products can be acquired at the following levels: Level 0 - meaning raw data; Level 1 – offers top-of-atmosphere radiometric and geometrically calibrated data; Level 2 – Geolocated and geocoded atmospheric correction.

Table 6. Prisma main characteristics (Adapted from Loizzo et al., 2018).

Instrument Main Characteristics	
Swath / FOV	30km / 2.45°
GSD	Hyperspectral : 30 m Pan : 5 m

Spatial Pixels	Hyperspectral: 1000 PAN: 6000
Spectral Range	VNIR: 400 – 1010 nm SWIR: 920 – 2505 nm
Spectral Resolution	≤ 12 nm
Spectral Bands	VNIR : 66 SWIR; 171
Radiometric Quantization	12 bit
VNIR SNR	> 200:1 on 400-1000 nm > 500:1 on 650 nm
SWIR SNR	> 200:1 on 1000-1750 nm > 400:1 on 1550 nm > 100:1 on 1950-2350 nm > 200:1 on 2100 nm
PAN SNR	> 240:1
Absolute Radiometric Accuracy	Better than 5%

The previously described hyperspectral sensors output images with low spatial resolution, having a pixel of 30x30 meters.

Spatial resolution underlies the capabilities of remote sensing techniques to identify scale-dependent variations in mapping. Decreased spatial resolution represents a loss of detail, making smaller characteristics harder or even impossible. Similarly, spectral detail is essential to differentiate some materials. In this way, a loss in spectral resolutions leads to losing the ability to distinguish some materials (Kruse et al., 2002). These parameters are of even greater importance in the case of spectral unmixing, a topic described in the next chapter.

It is also important to note that a linear increase in bands results in an exponential increase in the volume of features in the hyperspace. Taking into account that each new band represents an added dimension, this leads to a problem referred to in the literature as the Hughes phenomenon or the curse of dimensionality (Bishop, 2006).

Another noteworthy image characteristic is the radiometric resolution. This metric is derived from the number of bits the acquisition sensor uses to describe the radiance for each band. An increase in radiometric resolution can be seen as having an impact where the degree of confidence in the measurements is higher (Manolakis et al., 2003). The last resolution associated with satellite imagery is temporal, which refers to the time the satellite takes to return to the same point, measuring the time the sensor would take to acquire two different datasets for the same region.

An important notion is that rock spectra tend to have very different characteristics in contrast to their forming minerals. Still, in most cases, the most relevant absorption and reflective features are kept (Imanian et al., 2019). This topic is active in the remote sensing community even after extensive years of work; the complexity of this area is outside the scope of this work, but it's important to take into consideration when attempting spectral unmixing.

To finish this chapter, it is essential to understand that the most commonly described problem in remote sensing literature, especially in spectral unmixing (Chapter 6), is the lack of ground truth data. This happens because acquiring such data requires a lot of investment in terms of time and owning proper equipment to perform field measurements. Gewali et al. (2018) also describe two additional problems, the first being the lack of public hyperspectral datasets for researchers to validate and compare the performance of their models. The second one is described as difficulty in reproducing given studies due to the methods for implementation not being readily available, a topic that turned into a complementary objective of this work.

6. Endmember extraction and spectral unmixing

With direct application in fields such as exploration, mining, urban planning, agriculture, ecology, and space exploration, this section centers around analytical techniques applied to remote sensing data. Spectral unmixing relies on identifying different materials, due to the variations in their chemical and physical properties influencing how light is absorbed (Gewali et al., 2019).

The techniques focus on allowing for the decomposition of a given pixel into its possible constituent components. The term used to describe those pure independent members is endmember. It is crucial to understand that under a heterogeneous landscape, even with excellent spatial resolution, most spectrums associated with a given pixel in the image represent a mixture of different materials. For this reason, spectral unmixing techniques are built on the assumption that the spectral response of a given area (pixel) is a linear or nonlinear combination of the spectral signatures of each pure material present.

In regards to spectral unmixing, there are two options. The first is full spectral unmixing, a technique where we assume a system where every pure component spectrum is known, and even in this case, some variability is to be expected. Figure 37 provides an example of spectral unmixing while accepting some variability in the spectrum for the members present (Gewali et al., 2019). This intrinsic variability is related to unique characteristics that distinguish one instance of the material from another, even while belonging to the same category (Cochrane, 2000).

Figure 37. Spectral Unmixing and relative spectral variability (Gewali et al., 2019).

For most use cases for geologic purposes, the second option, partial spectral unmixing, is applied, based on knowing one specific material and having the algorithm identify a likelihood for the presence of that spectrum signature on each image pixel.

There are some possibilities for obtaining pure members. The most common ones either extract a pure spectrum from the image or use a spectrum for a given material from a library based on laboratory analysis. Due to the distortion associated with each step of image acquisition, it is often optimal to derive the endmember from the image and compare it with the spectrum from laboratory analysis (He et al., 2024), the reason for such a statement are the multiple distortions associated with not only atmospheric effects or image-specific characteristics but also sensor-specific characteristics and details in its calibration.

A description of the most typical approach for image classification in ENVI software can be seen in Figure 38:

Figure 38. ENVI image classification diagram.

6.1 Image endmember extraction

To derive endmembers from the image, a group of steps is needed, but the main idea in the case of this approach is based on identifying one or more pixels composed of a single material that would be a pure endmember for the image “dataset” being analysed. This approach has advantages compared to using analysis from a laboratory because using the data in the image dataset allows for extracting these members independently of distortions or characteristics of the sensor used for acquiring the image.

6.1.1 Spectral Reduction

Each image to be analyzed is composed of a set number of pixels. Each one has a given spectrum, consisting of a series of numbers representing the reflectance at different wavelengths. As described before, the spectrum obtained for each pixel of a certain image varies depending on the characteristics of the optical sensor.

As mentioned before, a problem in spectral data analysis is the curse of dimensionality. Under most circumstances, it is optimal to apply techniques that reduce the number of dimensions of the spectral data. This can be done due to the assumption that spectral bands oversample gradually varying reflectance at most wavelengths, removing unnecessary complexity while maintaining the most important features (Fauvel et al., 2013).

The more classic approach to this problem is the application of minimum noise fraction (MNF), which is ENVI’s default algorithm for spectral reduction. Although details of the transformation are proprietary, the focus is on segregating noise in the data, thereby reducing the computational requirements for further processing (Boardman & Kruse, 1994).

The algorithm is developed as a modified version of the studies from Green et al. (1988). The focus is divided into two different rotations, the first involves calculating the covariance matrix, to limit bands with a strong correlation. The process can be described as noise whitening (Hyvärinen & Oja, 2000). For the second rotation, a direct application of PCA is used, allowing the user to select the number of bands to use for further analysis based on the associated eigenvalues.

Another approach is to apply dimensionality reduction techniques described in the literature, which have proven their effectiveness across multiple areas. For this reason, two algorithms were tested, PCA and ICA.

In the case of PCA, it is a similar approach to the MNF case but excludes the covariance matrix correction. The main advantage of this algorithm, based on the works by Wold et al. (1987), is its ease of computation and simplicity in implementation, while being optimal for linear data.

Regarding the other algorithm tested for hyperspectral data reduction, ICA was developed by Comon (1994) as an algorithm designed to isolate independent components when working with signal data. With time, it proved its effectiveness across multiple domains of knowledge due to its ability to maximize the preservation of important patterns in data.

The loss of information can be evaluated by interpreting the associated eigenvalues of each reduced layer for PCA and MNF; for ICA applications, a kurtosis metric can achieve the same purpose (Hyvärinen & Oja, 2000). A more detailed description is presented in chapter 3.2.3 “Latent Linear Models”.

The problem that could be associated with using independent reduction techniques and not applying the covariance estimation and respective adjustments to noise leads to two possible scenarios:

1. If the image has a high signal-to-noise ratio across all bands, the implication from that rotation would not be of much significance, only causing more computation requirements without proper output improvements.
2. In the case of hyperspectral data, especially when certain bands have high levels of noise, an independent application allows for the usage and even testing of different noise band removal or even noise correction methods (Figure 39), something that could be explored in the future (Chen & Qian, 2008; He et al., 2024).

Figure 39. Denoising algorithm based on subspace representation and nonlocal low-rank tensor decomposition (He et al., 2024).

6.1.2 Spatial Dimensionality Reduction

There are two main chains of thought possible: either assuming there are pure pixels (that are composed of exactly one endmember only), or simulating how a possible pure endmember would be. For the context of this work, the first chain of thought will be the one applied, since it's the one that has been well established in geological studies for longer, for this reason only PPI (pixel purity index) will be described in detail since it is the most commonly used, and also the only option when working with ENVI software.

ENVI's approach to this problem, even though not publicly available, is known in the scientific literature to be based on projecting the vector pixels into multiple groups of skewers, those being an agglomeration of randomly generated pixel vectors in a context that maximizes the identification of the most extreme vectors (Plaza & Chang, 2005). Working with data in this way relies on two criteria: one is that it is accepted by default that at least one pixel in the image is composed of the single material we want to obtain the spectra, and the other problem is the uncertainty related to the choice of the number of skewers to use.

ENVI's algorithm has two different criteria to be selected by the user: the number of interactions and the threshold value. The number of interactions allows the user to manually select the number of skewers for the vector pixels that constitute the image to

be compared. The threshold value controls the limit beyond which both vectors can be divergent to still be considered pure (Exelis Visual Information Solutions, 2014).

This approach, while being the most commonly used, has the problems cited before, relying on the assumption that at least one pixel is composed of an actual material and having a subjective number of interactions and threshold value selected by the user, with even analysis done with the same parameters having different outputs due to the probabilistic nature from the use of a random set of vectors projected as skewers. The pure pixel assumption is also something that is not to be expected in the case of low spatial resolution images.

Various theoretical approaches have been described. Unfortunately, most of them fall short in real-world applications due to other limitations, such as requiring prior knowledge of the number of endmembers present in a given image. A mathematical approach for identifying what would be the real endmember, even in the case where none of the pixels are pure, is technically possible, with the main problem being that those approaches normally assume the data has no noise, underperforming when noise is included, something that is to be expected in the case of real-world data (Plaza et al., 2012)

6.1.3 Endmember Selection

Manual

For the final selection of pixels to be considered as endmembers, one approach is to project the point into a plane or space and have the user manually select the points due to visual inspection. Two problems emerge from this. One is that for data with dimensions higher than 3, to project the points visually, the user either (i) needs to manually select the bands being projected, leading to the user not being able to see the whole structure of the data at once, or (ii) the dimension needs to be reduced once again using techniques like PCA, leading to even more loss in information. Another problem is the low replicability of user selections due to the subjective criteria in the selection. Figure 40 shows an example of a scatter plot using results from PCA and the location of the respective endmembers (Sivakumar et al., 2022).

Figure 40. Manual endmember selection (Sivakumar et al., 2022).

Automatic

Using clustering algorithms to extract a group considered representative of an endmember has the advantage of the clusters being comprehended and analyzed in the higher-dimensional hyperplane.

ENVI's default use of K-means is an option that relies on the mean distance from the points to a given arbitrary point in space. This algorithm has shown minimal capability at replicating the manual selection, most of the time generating classes composed of 1 or 2 pixels due to the randomness associated with the algorithm's choice to select a point in space to use as the center for a given cluster.

6.2 Spectral Unmixing

The next and final step is to run an algorithm that outputs a metric for the likelihood of the target endmember being represented in each pixel. There are two main options to achieve this result, partial unmixing or total unmixing, both having their strong sides and disadvantages.

The use of full unmixing has a main practical issue related to assuming the user knows every endmember present in the image, a manageable task in some fields of study (Bioucas-Dias & Plaza, 2010), but with complex implementation in a geologic context (van der Meer, 2004).

The use of partial unmixing assumes the knowledge of one given endmember. Algorithms are built to output a metric for the likelihood of a given endmember being present in each given pixel. For this task, the ENVI software incorporates three main algorithms: Linear Spectral Unmixing (LSU), Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM), and Mixture Tuned Matched Filtering (MTMF).

6.2.1 Linear Spectral Unmixing

This model assumes that the measured spectrum for a given point in space is a linear combination of the pure constituents present, formally known as *endmembers*. If $x = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_K]$ represents the pixel spectra, $s = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_K]$ represents the endmember spectrum, and a_1, a_2, \dots, a_K are the correspondent abundances, them:

$$x = \sum_{k=1}^M a_k s_k + w$$

where w represents an error vector.

Li & Chang, (2015) describe the implementation of LSU with simplex volume implementations, an interesting approach requiring no outside noise from, for example, the sensor. There is the possibility of excluding outliers to account for this noise, but implementing outlier inspection without relying on user manual inspection is hard to achieve. It would most likely need to be fine-tuned for each case of study, losing part of its inherent value.

6.2.2 Spectral Angle Mapper

As described before, the spectral data can be seen as a cube with spatial-spectral characteristics, in a way that the observed surface reflectance data can be seen as a

scatter of points in a K -dimensional Euclidean space, \mathfrak{R}^K , where K represents the total number of spectral bands. Let vectors x and y be $[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_K]$ and $[y_1, y_2, \dots, y_K]$, respectively. In this way, we can describe the similarity between two given vectors that represent spectrums using SAM (Camps-Valls, 2016):

$$\angle(x, y) = \arccos \frac{x \cdot y}{\|x\| \|y\|}$$

where $x \cdot y$ is the dot product of vectors x and y .

Compared to the previous technique, the main advantage of this approach is that, due to its calculation being based on the angle between features, it is invariant to spectral changes associated with varying illumination intensities or angle orientations (Camps-Valls, 2016).

6.4.3 Mixture Tuned Matched Filtering

The last algorithm from ENVI software is MTMF. It has the advantage of joining two metrics, abundance and infeasibility, to state a reduction in false positives in the classification. In most cases, the statement turns out correct, showing the best performance out of all incorporated algorithms (Boardman, 1998). Unfortunately, the details of how each metric is calculated are proprietary.

6.4.4 Self-Proposed Algorithm

The intention with a partial spectral unmixing technique is to input an image and an “endmember” spectrum and generate an output that allows the user to classify each pixel. For this case, the input is a set of two variables, composed of a two-dimensional array that represents the image, and a target spectrum “endmember”, and the objective is to generate an output composed of two variables: one is a list of values that indicate how similar the spectrum of each pixel is to the spectra “endmember”, and another measuring how valid the output is in terms of physical meaning.

With input X , representing a given image, each component $X(i)$ is a vector of length n , this being the number of spectral bands.

Let t be a vector like each component of X , in this case, a single spectrum of length n represents the endmember.

Normalization of the vectors is mandatory for further analysis. The implications of this process will be better understood in later parts of this description.

$$Z(i, j) = \frac{(X(i, j) - \cup j)}{\sigma j} \tag{1}$$

where $\cup j$ represents the mean for the value of a given band j in the entire set, and σj is the standard deviation under the same context. This transformation results in Z , which is composed of the normalized version of each vector pixel from the image. The same transformation is also applied to the endmember spectrum represented by t .

With this information, the covariance matrix can be calculated as follows:

$$C = \frac{1}{N} . Z^T . Z \tag{2}$$

where, N is the Length of X (the number of pixels) and Z^T represents the transposition of matrix Z across itself (Anton, 2010).

The multiplication of $Z^T . Z$ has the physical meaning of having each component $X(i, j)$ representing the multiplication of band i and band j across all data. From this result, a matrix C where each element $C(i, j)$ represents the correlation between each given band and each other as shown below.

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} C(1,1) & \dots & C(1,j) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ C(i,1) & \dots & C(i,j) \end{pmatrix} \tag{3}$$

In the context of this work, we want to achieve C^{-1} , a matrix where each component represents how independent each band is of the others. This process was done by computing the pseudo-inverse with NumPy (Oliphant, 2015) inverse covariation calculation. This approach avoids cases where infinitesimal calculations would delay the calculation process and cause unnecessary numerical errors.

There are several possibilities for estimating abundance, such as the algorithms described previously, including LSU and SAM. Another alternative is to use a match filter (*MF*) (Chang, 2003), a technique developed by the signal processing community, that is mathematically equivalent to the Constrained Energy Minimization described by Harsayni (1993). A MF metric can be calculated with the data achieved until this point.

$$MF = Z \cdot C^{-1} \cdot t' \tag{4}$$

The result from this calculation implies that the list MF has a length equal to the number of pixels of the original image, and each value represents how similar each pixel vector is to the vector representing the “endmember” when readjusted by the inverse covariance.

Until now, the results have produced a value that associates the similarity between spectrums. However, it does not account for the possible divergence between the nonmatching component and the background. For this reason, it is useful in unmixing algorithms to add a threshold value that compares to the background (Manolakis et al., 2003). To achieve this task, a background divergence metric (*BD*) is implemented to reduce false positive cases. The calculations to achieve such a task are described as follows:

$$\hat{u} = \frac{t}{\|t\|_2} \tag{5}$$

where u is a unit Euclidean vector that points in the direction of the standardized endmember spectrum in the n -dimensional space.

With Z being the matrix that contains the normalized version of each pixel in the image, a direct comparison with the vector u can be obtained as follows:

$$a = Z \cdot \hat{u} \tag{6}$$

In this way, any value:

$$a_{(i,j)} = Z_{(i,j)} \cdot \hat{u} \tag{7}$$

giving a quantitative metric to the components of the endmember vector that overlap with the pixel vector.

Using the same approach, now we can subtract the residual part (R):

$$R = Z - a\hat{u} \quad (8)$$

where any pixel is

$$R_{(i,j)} = Z_{(i,j)} - a_{(i,j)} \cdot \hat{u} \quad (9)$$

The final step is to measure this residual product against the background. To achieve the BD metric, the Mahalanobis distance is used to measure how anomalous the residual product is when adjusted to the background (Reed & Yu, 1990).

$$BD_{(i,j)} = R_{(i,j)} \cdot C^{-1} \cdot R_{(i,j)}^T \quad (10)$$

where $R_{(i,j)}^T$ is the transpose of the vector $R_{(i,j)}$. This ensures that proper matrix multiplication is possible by converting the row vector into a column vector.

Finally, the matching between MF and BD allows for selecting pixels where abundance is high and the residual part matches the background noise, which is expected to reduce false positives considerably. Currently under testing and showing promising results.

7. Methodology

7.1 Hyperspectral Data Acquisition and Pre-processing

An EnMap image was requested to evaluate the contribution of hyperspectral images in retrieving information related to the mineralization. Two images were received with an acquisition date of 26-01-2025 at 11:59:58 UTC and 14-02-2025 at 11:53:10 UTC, respectively.

The first image had a cloud coverage extending almost the entire image; for this reason, only the second image was used throughout this dissertation. The second image (Figure 42) highlights the Aramo plateau, the central zone of study. It is also important to notice that the image contains multiple dark spots corresponding to shadow zones when the image was captured.

The image comprises 224 bands, ranging across the VNIR and SWIR (from about 420 to 2445 nm), with a spatial resolution of 30m. The image was provided at level L2A, meaning that the atmospheric correction and orthorectification had already been performed.

As a result of the atmospheric correction, some bands were corrected to zero (Figure 41), and later a spectral subset was performed to remove bands 130 to 136. The pixels from the shadow zones essentially contain no hyperspectral information, as the values for each band are essentially zeros with some noise (Figure 41B).

Figure 41. x-axis - bands; y-axis - reflectance; A) Hyperspectral signal associated with a normal pixel. B) Hyperspectral signal associated with a pixel composed of shadow.

Figure 42. EnMap image with red circles indicating shadow zones.

7.1.1 Denoising, Inpainting, and Super-Resolution

As a means of improving some image characteristics with the intention of later understanding their impact on final results and overall analysis, the Deep Image Prior algorithm (source code: <https://github.com/DmitryUlyanov/deep-image-prior>) (Ulyanov et al., 2020) was used.

The model provides functions to perform denoising, inpainting (simulating missing spots), and super-resolution (upsampling the image to improve spatial resolution). The main requirement was for the image to be clipped (spatial subset) to a square with the number of horizontal/vertical pixels being a square of 2. Therefore, the original EnMap image was clipped to an extent that features 256x256 pixels (at 30x30 meters each), which features the area highlighted previously in Figure 42 (close-up view).

The first step featured performing denoising and inpainting. A mask featuring the shadow regions was used to signal the missing spots in the image. For this process, the model performed 20000 interactions and self-trained on a total of 3276896 parameters.

After this process, super-resolution was performed, resulting in images with upscale factors of 2 and 4, respectively, representing final results of 512x512 pixels (15x15 m) and 1024x1024 pixels (7.5x7.5 m) (Figure 49). For the upscaling, 20000 iterations were used, with the models training on a total of 2384452 parameters.

7.2 Retrieving information from hyperspectral data

All the steps described during this chapter were performed on the 3 different images generated in the previous section. From this point onward, the description and example images are from the analysis on the 512x512 (15x15m) pixel image; The same processes are repeated for the three different resolutions (30m,15m, 7.5m) to later evaluate the effect on MPM performance.

7.2.1 Unsupervised Clustering

Clustering algorithms are a practical way to separate an image into clusters that represent its main components. K-means and ISODATA are fast distance-based

clustering algorithms that, depending on the input parameters, can ensure all or almost all the points are classified into a cluster.

OPTICS was also tested, although a special consideration must be made since this type of algorithm tends to exclude a significant part of the dataset from the classified group.

The methods used are included in AetherGeo v1.0. K-means implementation (K-means++) only requires the number of clusters to be predetermined. A value of 7 was used as the parameter for the number of clusters for this study since, after visual inspection, the clusters isolated the main components properly (such as soil, vegetation, rock outcrop, etc). Further description is present in chapter 8.1.2. For OPTICS, hyperparameter selection can be tricky. Figure 43 provides an example function that can be used for the automatic selection of hyperparameters.

```

89 def select_parameters(data):
90     """Automatically determine OPTICS parameters based on data characteristics.
91
92     Parameters:
93         data: numpy.ndarray (n_samples, n_features)
94
95     Returns:
96         dict: Dictionary containing optimized OPTICS parameters
97     """
98     n_samples, n_features = data.shape
99
100    k = min(n_samples - 1, 10)
101    nbrs = NearestNeighbors(n_neighbors=k).fit(data)
102    distances, _ = nbrs.kneighbors(data)
103    avg_distance = np.mean(distances[:, 1:])
104
105    min_samples = max(
106        5, # Absolute minimum
107        2 * n_features, # Scale with dimensionality
108        int(np.sqrt(n_samples) * 0.1) # Scale with dataset size
109    )
110
111    # Lower xi for sparse data, higher for dense data
112    xi = min(0.1, max(0.01, avg_distance / np.std(distances[:, 1:])))
113
114    if n_samples < 100:
115        min_cluster_size = 0.1 # 10% for small datasets
116    elif n_samples < 1000:
117        min_cluster_size = 0.05 # 5% for medium datasets
118    else:
119        min_cluster_size = 0.02 # 2% for large datasets
120
121    params = {
122        'min_samples': min_samples,
123        'xi': xi,
124        'min_cluster_size': min_cluster_size
125    }
126
127    return params

```

Figure 43. Function for automatic selection of OPTICS hyperparameters.

7.2.2 Dimensionality Reduction

Unsupervised learning algorithms such as PCA and ICA are potent techniques that enable spectral dimensionality reduction, providing an outcome containing a set number

of bands (fewer than the original input) while aiming to preserve the most important signals present in the original dataset.

The outcomes from this process will be used directly as independent input features for the integration algorithms to perform MPM. They also serve another purpose as they can be used as inputs for the endmember extraction clouds (see “7.2.3 – Endmember Extraction and Partial Spectral Unmixing”).

In AetherGeo v1.0, a graph representing a significance value for each new band was generated after selecting the number of components (5 performed well at preserving the information in this case) and running a dimensionality reduction function. In the case of PCA, the results are ordered and represent the explained variance ratio of each new component (Figure 44A). In contrast, the results are not ordered for ICA, and a kurtosis value is used for significance (Figure 44B) (Santos et al., 2025). A total of two datasets, comprising 5 PCA bands and 5 ICA bands, were generated and kept as inputs for the MPM algorithm.

Figure 44. a) PCA explained variance rate for each component. B) Kurtosis as a metric for evaluating ICA band significance.

7.2.3 Endmember extraction and partial spectral unmixing

Figure 45 illustrates a workflow developed to perform both endmember extraction and partial spectral unmixing using AtherGeo v1.0 (Santos et al., 2025). SAM was considered a partial unmixing technique under the presumption that the similarity between two spectra (endmember and pixel, respectively) directly indicates a higher abundance of the material characterized by that spectrum in the region represented by its respective pixel.

Figure 45. Workflow for image classification. (A): K-means results with seven classes; (B): selection of the extreme points (endmembers in purple color) in the 3D point cloud; (C): spectral library of selected endmembers; (D): 2D plot feature to extract SAM results with a smaller angle (red); (E): final results with target areas in red (Santos et al., 2025).

To replicate this workflow in the context of the EnMap datasets generated (Section 7.1), the K-means results for 7 classes described previously were used, skipping steps 2 and 3 (Preprocess and Clustering, respectively). Each resulting K-means class, some in pairs (described in chapter 7.3) was used for the masking step. The parametrization of the PPI step was based on the data size used for the endmember extraction cloud, as described below. The next step was to perform the endmember extraction on the original datasets, applying the default protocol in AetherGeo, which uses Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) to generate a 3D embedding. Alternatively, the user could use PCA/ICA results in place of the full datasets before generating the embedding in this step.

An example of the step-by-step process after obtaining the K-means clustering results goes as follows:

A binary layer containing a single K-means class was created for each class. In the case of cluster 4, the pixels belonging to that case can be seen in Figure 46A. Figure 46B shows the pixels that were considered pure after performing PPI using the original image as input and the cluster 5 image as a mask. The PPI analysis was performed using 8192 projections. 302 pure pixels were identified from an initial set of 15,000 (Figure 47).

Figure 46. A) K-means after performing a query to isolate class 4. B) Results from using K-means class 4 as a mask for PPI.

Figure 47. PPI analysis performed on AetherGeo v1.0.

The Point Cloud Extraction function in AetherGeo allowed the generation of a 3D embedding (showing the relationship between the data associated with each pixel) and manually selecting the cloud borders representing the different endmembers. Figure 48 shows the 3D point cloud using the 15,000 pixels related to the K-means class 4 mask and the 302 pure pixels derived from PPI (a and c, respectively). Meanwhile, the resulting manually selected endmember for each point cloud shared similar results, as expected (b and d, respectively). After this step, the spectral library is saved (in this case, only one of them, since the results are from the same class). This process was repeated for the other K-means classes.

a)

b)

c)

d)

Figure 48. a) 3D point cloud with 15,000 pixels. c) 3D point cloud with 302 pixels after PPI application. b and d) endmembers derived from selecting the cloud borders, for point clouds in a and c, respectively.

Two algorithms were considered to perform the partial spectral unmixing step: SAM and the self-proposed algorithm (described in 6.4.4). Also, two approaches can be followed: (i) employing the algorithm and working with the results as numerical values, and (ii) performing a classification, usually by applying a threshold to the numerical results.

Since SAM measures a single variable (the angle between the two vectors in latent space), where a smaller value indicates a higher likelihood of the endmember material being present, the selection is simple (Figure 45D), but deciding on the threshold can be subjective. The self-proposed algorithm is considered an alternative to replace SAM, following a different selection criterion that mixes the two variables associated with each pixel. The selection for that case follows a pattern similar to MTMF. This process tends to reduce false positives and provides an easier way of recognizing the pattern associated with true positive values (Figure 49). For the case of MTMF, even with attempts to provide automatic selection based on ML algorithms, manual selection outperformed by a considerable margin (Routh et al., 2018).

Figure 49. An example scatterplot of artificially generated MF and infeasibility values (Routh et al., 2018). a) Selection based on a cone shape. b) Inverse shape used in research for selection.

From the process of retrieving endmembers using the method previously described, 17 endmembers were retrieved, performing visual inspection highlighted that those spectral signatures were related to multiple occurring materials in the region, some highly related to rock outcrops and soil, but others were related to, for example, vegetation and other non-geologic materials. Section 8.1.4 provides a further analysis of the results from spectral unmixing using these endmembers as inputs, either applying any form of classification or using the numerical values directly.

This work used SAM for partial unmixing and to prepare the datasets to integrate through MPM. This is because with SAM, for each endmember, only a single variable is generated (17 resulting input features). In contrast, with the self-proposed algorithm, two variables are generated for each endmember, resulting in 34 input features. The lower number of input features contributes to a lower model complexity.

7.3 Additional dataset preparation

QGIS v3.28 was used to prepare additional geological and structural datasets/input features for MPM. This included coordinate transformations, data vectorization and rasterization, spatial queries, and proximity analysis.

Some additional custom processing tools were employed in Python, for example, to extract the density of structural features. These include Geopandas (Bossche et al., 2025), Numpy (Oliphant, 2015), Rasterio (Gillies et al., 2013), SciPy (Virtanen et al., 2020), and Shapely (Gillies et al., 2022). The Python code for dataset preparation is provided together with the algorithms for MPM under: <https://github.com/GoncaloAzSantos/ML-for-Mineral-Predictivity-Mapping>.

The steps to generate derived datasets (described in Table 7) include:

- Manual vectorization of a recent geological map (Figure 50), faults and thrusts, and the lithological contact between the two main lithological units that compose the Plateau (Figure 51).
- Using the algorithms mentioned earlier to generate new datasets that contain information such as buffers and line density (Figure 52).

Figure 50. Aramo lithological map.

Figure 51. A) Main lithological contact. B) Contact Buffer.

Figure 52. A) Buffer regarding the local faults; B) Faults and Thrust density map.

All data in vector format was rasterized to a spatial resolution of 30, 15 and 7.5 m while respecting the same extent of the original EnMap Image. Doing this work and ensuring proper input data quality before data integration is crucial, as data quality is as important as the robustness of the conceptual model for target identification (Yousefi *et al.* 2021).

At this point, the maps prepared for data integration are the following:

Table 7. Input layers used for MPM.

	Number of input layers	Description
Lithological Map	1	Contains the base map geology based on Figure 50.
Contact Buffer	1	A buffer based on the distance from contact that separates the two most prevalent lithological units in the Plateau up to 1500m distance.
Buffers from fault and thrust features	3	Contains a buffer up to 1750 m from faults, thrusts, and a combination of both: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Faults_Buffer_Distance (Faults) - Thrust_Buffer_Distance (Thrusts) - All_Buffer_Distance (Combination of both)
Fault density maps	3	Density maps for faults, thrusts, and a combination of both: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Faults_Line_Density (Faults) - Thrust_Line_Density (Thrusts) - All_Line_Density (Combination of both)
K-means results	1	A layer where each pixel has its respective K-means cluster as a value.
Dimensionality reduction results	10	Results from PCA aiming for a total of 5 components, and input layers generated with ICA, also using 5 as the number of components.
Partial spectral unmixing results	17	SAM results for the 17 endmembers acquired across different spectral libraries

		derived from the image using endmember extraction following the methodology described in chapter 7.2.3.
Height variation maps from LiDAR data (Azzalini et al., 2024)	1	Maps measuring the variation in terrain height from 2015 to 2023 (Figure 53).

Height Variation Map (using LiDAR)

Figure 53. Height variation map developed using LiDAR data from 2015 to 2023 (Azzalini et al., 2024).

7.4 MPM

As mentioned before, the models tested for MPM were SVM, RF, XGBoost, CatBoost, and MLP. They all share similar conditions regarding how input data is loaded and pre-processed. Some models, such as the MLP, have additional metrics from the training process. Figure 54 illustrates the workflow for the MPM approach. The following sub-sections give a step-by-step overview of the process. The Python code for algorithm implementation for MPM is available at: <https://github.com/GoncaloAzSantos/ML-for-Mineral-Predictivity-Mapping>.

Figure 54. MPM workflow.

7.4.1 Pre-processing

S341 project partners provided a spreadsheet containing data from geochemical analysis performed on samples collected during extensive field campaigns. In this work, the criterion for distinguishing between mineralized and non-mineralized samples was based on the values for Co, Cu, and Ni, being at least 0.05%, 0.4%, and 0.07% respectively. After this process, points close to other ones were merged into polygons (Figure 55), respecting the geospatial context those points represented. The final process was rasterizing the result into images at the three different spatial resolutions to be tested.

Figure 55. Division between mineralized and non-mineralized points after applying the mentioned criterion.

All scripts start by loading (i) the file with the training targets (in this case if the pixel has the value 1 associated it represents a mineralized spot, 0 represents non-mineralized, and -1 represents pixels without information), (ii) the input features described in section 7.3 (as all valid files in a predetermined input feature directory) and (iii) an optional binary mask to be applied (in this case, a mask featuring the regions containing the Plateau).

This step involves splitting the training data into a training group (70%) and a testing group (30%) using the “train_test_split” function from scikit-learn (Pedregosa et al., 2011).

To improve class imbalance in the training group Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE, Figure 56) (Chawla et al., 2002) was applied using a sampling strategy set to 0.5. For the 15m resolution data with a 70/30 training/validation split, the number of points for the minority class went from 100 to half the number of the majority class (so a total of 198 points in this case).

Figure 56. Illustration of SMOTE (Aldraimli et al., 2020).

7.4.1.1 Feature Selection

In the first components of the script, the user can set the variable “FEATURE_SELECTION” to either True or False. If set to false, the script will use all input features to train the model and build predictions. Optionally, if set to true, the user can provide a value under the variable “N_FEATURES_TO_SELECT” to limit the number of input features (organized by significance) based on results from previous analysis.

7.4.2 Model training

Due to limitations on the amount of training data, hyperparameter tuning techniques were not considered, as they would force the data split into having a train, test, and validation sets, something that would further decrease the amount of training data while also testing and validating the results on very limited sets in terms of data points.

For this reason, hyperparameters were manually set based on documentation recommendations and some manual testing. Figure 57 highlights the hyperparameters used for the different algorithms tested.

XGBoost	CatBoost	MLP
max_depth = 0, learning_rate = 0.1, n_estimators = 300, subsample = 0.9, colsample_bytree = 0.7, gamma = 0.2, reg_alpha = 0.1, reg_lambda = 0.5, scale_pos_weight = 1, eval_metric = "logloss", use_label_encoder = False random_state = 42	Interactions = 500, learning_rate = 0.05, depth = 6, L2_lead_reg = 3, random_seed = 42, verbose = 100, auto_class_weights = "Balanced", loss_function = "Logloss", early_stopping_rounds = 20	hidden_layer_sizes = (256, 128, 64), activation = "relu", solver = "adam", alpha = 0.001, batch_size = 256, learning_rate = "adaptive", learning_rate_init = 0.001, max_iter = 1000, early_stopping = True, validation_fraction = 0.15, n_iter_no_change = 30, tol = 1e-5, random_state = 42, verbose = True
RF		SVM
n_estimators = 200, max_depth = 20, min_sample_split = 5, min_sample_leaf = 2, class_weight = "balanced", random_state = 42, n_jobs = -1		kernel = "linear", C = 1.0, probability = True, random_state = 42

Figure 57. Hyperparameters used XGBoost, CatBoost, MLP, RF, and SVM.

7.4.3 Optimizations and Model Evaluation

After this step, a threshold value is defined based on maximizing the F1-score. This threshold is used to generate binary results to calculate performance metrics.

Based on the confusion matrix values, precision, recall, and F1-score are calculated, as well as the ROC AUC and PR AUC. All the results and predictions (numerical and binary) are saved to a diagnostics directory previously set at the start of the script.

7.4.4 Feature Analysis

Using the statistical analysis from SciPy (Virtanen et al., 2020), this last step evaluated the contribution from different inputs to the model outcomes. Two important statistical measures are calculated to achieve this outcome: the Pearson correlation coefficient and the p-value.

The Pearson correlation coefficient measures the linear relationship between the input feature and the target; in this case, the correlation can be positive or negative, ranging from -1 to 1 for perfect correlations. The p-value is different since it provides a metric for statistical significance that can measure non-linear relationships. A value of 0.01 indicates a highly significant relationship between variables, while a p-value greater than 0.05 indicates a very low or non-significant relationship.

8. Results

8.1 Hyperspectral Data Analysis

8.1.1 Denoising, Inpainting, and Super-Resolution

Figure 58 highlights the results from inpainting and performing super-resolution. Both upscaling attempts required about the same time (measuring to an almost exact 5 hours), but they were conducted on machines with significantly different characteristics. The 2x upscaling was performed on a laptop with an RTX 4050 6GB, while the 4x upscaling was performed on a desktop with an RTX 5070ti 16GB.

Attempting to perform the 4x upscaling on a network with the amount of hidden layers doubled (leading to 8947624 parameters) led to an active amount of used video random access memory (VRAM) above GPU limitations. This increase in model size and loss in efficiency due to data leakage made the processing time go from 5 hours to an estimated time of 2 weeks; for this reason, further testing stopped. For this reason both the 2x and 4x upscaling were performed in a network of the same complexity (2384452 parameters).

Figure 58. Different levels of upscaling and the effect of inpainting on the EnMap image.

8.1.2 Unsupervised Clustering

K-means was used during this step; its reliability, efficient computing even in large datasets, and ease of parameter selection make the algorithm ideal for a first interaction with a new dataset. The outcomes displayed in Figure 59 are significant as they were used for the endmember extraction and also as one of the inputs for MPM. When

comparing the results with the EnMap image (Attachment D, Figure 71), it is possible to notice some patterns:

- Cluster 4 clearly isolates the zones in the plateau where each pixel seems to be mostly comprised of rock outcrop.
- Cluster 7 seems to be mainly composed of pixels from areas where the soil has a brown/reddish colour brown.
- Cluster 2, on the other hand, seems to be a mix of landcover types that changes from a greyish to a bit greenish pixel color depending on small changes in the bands used for RGB display. These pixels seem composed of a mixture of soil, low vegetation, and possibly even rock outcrop.
- The other clusters seem to feature vegetation and some darker spots (due to terration inclination) that still had significant spectral information and therefore were not excluded in the shadow mask before inpainting.

Figure 59. K-means results.

OPTICS was also considered for this step. Due to the algorithm's properties, it does not scale well for analyzing big datasets, making its use unviable for the first analysis performed on the entire dataset.

8.1.3 Dimensionality reduction

For dimensionality reduction, both ICA and PCA were used to retrieve 5 components; the significance metrics for each new component, as provided while performing the

analysis on AetherGeo v1.0, can be seen in Figure 45 (Section 7.2.2). A direct analysis of the new bands can provide a significant interpretation of the association between geological characteristics, especially outcrop regions, which are mainly highlighted in the first components of PCA (which explain most of the variance). Different bands also highlight the soil variations.

Figure 60 shows that the first two PCA components (Figure 60B and C) are highly associated with the local geological outcrops (especially component 2). At the same time, component 1 gives a strong signal in the plateau's internal part and highlights some of the soils, especially in the south-west part, where there is the most exposure. Component number 5 from ICA generated a map that is particularly similar to PCA component 1.

Figure 60. a) EnMap Image. b) PCA component 1 showing a high correlation with local outcrops and soil. c) PCA component 2 isolates the outcrop components in the plateau. d) ICA component 5 with results similar to PCA component 1.

Some limitations to this analysis include bands with particularly high noise levels, sometimes even with a characteristic spatial distribution (Attachment D, Figure 72B). Other bands might be based on signals unrelated to the local geology (Attachment D, Figure 72C).

8.1.5 Partial spectral unmixing

The self-proposed algorithm enables an easier selection and might even reduce the number of false positives compared to SAM. Although the self-proposed algorithm might have benefits for analysis focused purely on remote sensing, the SAM results were selected for data integration. The double variable nature injured its use in data integration due to doubling the number of input variables.

Figure 61 shows the different selection methods for the algorithms tested and the effects on the final classification results.

Figure 61. A) SAM; B) Self-proposed algorithm.

8.2 MPM

The first analysis was performed at a scale of 15x15 m. Figure 62 highlights the results of the XGBoost implementation for MPM using 25 and 37 inputs. Overall, all the algorithms generated maps that share common patterns, but the variation in performance is significant. The prediction matrix can be found under Attachment D, Figure 73.

Table 8 shows the performance variations between models (Figure 64):

Table 8. Model performance metrics using 25 input features and a spatial resolution of 15 m.

XGBoost						
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support	ROC AUC	PR AUC
Non-mineralized	0.97	0.96	0.96	170	0.977	0.921
Mineralized	0.84	0.88	0.86	43		
CatBoost						
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support	ROC AUC	PR AUC
Non-mineralized	0.95	0.98	0.97	170	0.975	0.954
Mineralized	0.92	0.79	0.85	43		
RF						
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support	ROC AUC	PR AUC
Non-mineralized	0.97	0.97	0.97	170	0.987	0.927
Mineralized	0.88	0.88	0.88	43		
SVM						
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support	ROC AUC	PR AUC
Non-mineralized	0.94	0.97	0.95	170	0.953	0.857
Mineralized	0.86	0.74	0.80	43		
MLP						
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support	ROC AUC	PR AUC
Non-mineralized	0.96	0.95	0.96	170	0.952	0.953
Mineralized	0.82	0.86	0.84	43		

Figure 62. XGBoost results for MPM at 15m spatial resolution using a different number of input features.

Figure 63. XGBoost (25 input features, 15 m resolution) ROC.

The intention was to perform MPM at three different scales, 30, 15, and 7.5 m. Unfortunately, at 30 m, the criterion for the minimum number of samples per class was not met by the mineralized class, making the analysis unviable.

At 7.5 m, the performance metrics are great in terms of values (Table 9), but unfortunately, the image loses spatial coherence, and the values are more extreme overall. Due to this, it seems like the model at this spatial resolution managed to overfit due to the similarity between points in the training data; similar results occur with the other algorithms tested. Similar to the results when using the inputs with 15 m (Figure 64), the correlation between the results from the different algorithms is very high (visual evaluation).

Table 9. Model performance metrics using 25 input features and a spatial resolution of 7.5 m.

XGBoost						
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support	ROC AUC	PR AUC
Non-mineralized	0.98	1	0.99	654	0.995	0.961
Mineralized	0.98	0.93	0.96	175		
CatBoost						
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support	ROC AUC	PR AUC
Non-mineralized	0.98	1	0.99	654	0.997	0.964
Mineralized	0.99	0.93	0.96	175		
RF						
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support	ROC AUC	PR AUC
Non-mineralized	0.97	0.98	0.98	654	0.990	0.940
Mineralized	0.93	0.90	0.91	175		
SVM						
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support	ROC AUC	PR AUC
Non-mineralized	0.93	0.89	0.91	654	0.862	0.811
Mineralized	0.64	0.73	0.68	175		
MLP						
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support	ROC AUC	PR AUC
Non-mineralized	0.98	0.97	0.98	654	0.986	0.955
Mineralized	0.90	0.94	0.92	175		

Figure 64. A) EnMap Image; B) XGBoost results; C) RF results; D) CatBoost results; E) MLP results; F) SVM results.

Figure 63 shows the MPM results for XGBoost using inputs and training data at a scale of 7.5 m.

Figure 65. MPM using XGBoost and inputs at a scale of 7.5 m.

8.2.1 Significance analysis and correlation with the mineralization

This component helps understand how the different input features are related to the mineralization (Figure 66), and the impact those features later had on the model's decisions (Figure 67). The results displayed here are from the analysis made using the XGBoost with 25 input features and a spatial resolution of 15 m.

According to the kurtosis analysis, ICA 4 had a very high significance (Figure 45), something that also happened with the significance metric in relation to the mineralization (although the correlation is negative).

PCA 5 was very related to vegetation; the significance and correlation with mineralization is low, something that was expected considering that medium to large-scale vegetation is rare in the mineralized zones of the Plateau. As for PCA 4, similar results were obtained, but this component was very related to noise in this case.

Figure 66. Correlation and significance analysis between input features and the mineralization.

Another important thing to notice is that the endmembers that resulted from an extraction performed using k-means results (as a mask), which isolated outcrop and soil regions, tend to have high positive correlations. In contrast, the ones associated with medium to large-scale vegetation tend to have low correlation and significance values.

The results related to endmembers also rarely share the same correlation and significance value, even for endmembers derived from similar parts of the image (for example, outcrops or soils). This indicates that the methods for endmember extraction captured small details that led to the different unmixing outcomes.

It is also important to notice that the inputs related to structural data (buffers and density maps) tend to have a high importance in the model's decision, something expected especially taking into consideration the close relationship between these features and the mineralization. At the scale of 7.5 m the results in general increased the importance of those input features.

Figure 67. Feature importance analysis for XGBoost using data with 15 m spatial resolution.

Using the height variation map as an input led to interesting findings. A study that was initially focused on studying the local geomorphology led to an input that not only showed a strong correlation and significance in relation to the mineralization, but also shares very high importance scores in the models' decisions. The negative correlation matches internal information provided by experts working on the ground in this specific mineralization, where areas with less height variation would get priority for field work exploration.

For further field work, the target areas proposed from the results of this work would be the ones represented in Figure 68:

XGBoost with 25 inputs

Figure 68. Map containing two new areas (red ellipses) that could be targets for future exploration field work.

9. Discussion and future works

As for denoising and upscaling, in the case of the model used, although the authors incentivize testing variations in network design and other hyperparameters, the computational time can be a drawback, especially in the case of larger input datasets and increments in the number of parameters. In the future, testing other models or exploring the analysis in deeper, more complex networks could be beneficial, especially for high levels of upscaling.

Spatial resolution proved to be a crucial factor for MPM. In this case, inpaintings were used to correct shadow regions; under other scenarios, it could be expanded to other regions. The increase in spatial resolution appear to have been limited by computational power and image detail; fusion algorithms could possibly provide a greater way of improving spatial resolution (Ghassemian, 2016). Ultra-high-resolution fusion (for example, using World-View 3 data) with hyperspectral data is a possibility that hasn't been explored extensively until now. Some of the latest alternatives for improving spatial resolution, such as Hyperspectral-SAR and triple way fusion (using multispectral, hyperspectral, and SAR), could also be explored in the future due to the very high potential for improving spatial resolution.

Further testing on clustering and dimensionality reduction techniques could be of great use. GMMs or other probabilistic approaches could lead to different insights or even contribute as independent input features for the MPM algorithms. For dimensionality reduction, exploring variations in the number of components could be useful. Testing different algorithms, such as non-negative matrix factorization (NMF), self-organizing map (SOM), or minimum noise fraction (MNF), could expand or be of use, especially in studies dedicated to dimensionality reduction techniques in remote sensing.

Endmember extraction techniques can provide insights into the different components of an image without requiring field measures; in this way, they were useful as a data-driven way of acquiring input features. Some of those endmembers were more related to the mineralization than others. In the correlation and importance analysis, the unmixing results related to endmembers that were closely related to geology (outcrops and soil) shared higher values, while the ones related to, for example, vegetation showed lower values.

Although the unmixing results used for integration were from SAM, the new self-proposed algorithm could lead to similar classification results while providing an easier

selection method. Further testing and applications on different images/test sites would be needed for further conclusions. As for the use in MPM, performing classification on all the unmixing results and using those results as inputs instead of the raw numerical values could lead to different results; further testing is needed.

In terms of input features for MPM, in this case, the only types of inputs that didn't show significance, correlation, or importance were the k-means classes and the geological base map (contrary to the contact buffer, which showed the most significance and correlation). This last one is not expected to be the case across different types of mineralizations.

The features from remote sensing were important for the MPM algorithms; extending to other sensors, such as PRISMA or multispectral satellites, could be useful, but careful attention to the number of input features would be needed.

Overall, the algorithms related to decision trees performed the best, but the other models weren't outperformed by an extensive margin. All results from different algorithms share common patterns, a good identification, and something that highlights the capacity of all the models to recognize patterns.

The results showed great performance in terms of mathematical validation; moreover, the patterns recognized by the algorithms coincide with locally known mineralizations and also make sense from a geological point of view.

The data integration algorithms can also give us precious information about what variables are contributing the most to the occurrence of these deposits, giving us feedback for geologists to understand the dynamics behind the mineralization. Since the approach to acquire input data (excluding training data) was mainly focused on data-driven methods, these already trained models could be tested for MPM in new greenfield zones, helping decide where to start when accessing a completely new study pilot. Also, the model parameters after training can be saved; therefore, a similar analysis can be made in different regions.

In the future, consideration for inputs that are not as conditioned by superficial variations (mostly vegetation for hyperspectral remote sensing) could be considered for MPM; such inputs could be aerial magnetics, radiometry, or gravimetric variation maps.

10. Conclusions

With easier access to hyperspectral satellite data due to recent missions such as EnMap and PRISMA, it's possible to acquire data about the variation in materials, or material composition, something with immense value for studies in fields directly related to geology.

Various methods for data-driven hyperspectral data analysis generated valuable results for the implementation in MPM. This highlights that important information related to lithological and mineralogical variations can be acquired for extensive areas of study due to sensors onboard satellites.

Spatial resolution was the main problem when working with the hyperspectral data; in this regard, a super-resolution approach was applied, which led to interesting insights. Trying to improve the resolution to values smaller than 15 m was a problem due to model complexity; in the future, other approaches deserve further testing.

The contribution of this research can be expanded into additional research areas, considering that remote sensing can be applied to most materials at the surface level.

MPM turned out to be successful, considering the mathematical validation metrics achieved. All the results from different algorithms tested also share similar patterns and high prospectivity areas. Future studies could include field validation.

In conclusion, this dissertation provides two main benefits to the scientific community. Those can be described as follows:

- One is by providing new predictive maps developed by exploring the potential of multiple algorithms for integrating remote sensing, structural, and lithological data. The results generated also validated the potential of spectral unmixing techniques for mapping the occurrence and respective abundance of different materials across the study region based on the impact such information has on the final MPM for Aramo's Co-Ni-Cu mineralization.
- The second one is a new set of tools, operating as standalone software that benefits the educational and scientific community with a set of functionalities that were previously not easily accessible.

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Attachments

Attachment A – Geological map at 1:50 000 scale

Figure 69. Geologic map number 52 of Spain – Proaza region (Pello, 1973).

Attachment B – Published Materials

Article

AetherGeo: A Spectral Analysis Interface for Geologic Mapping

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Abstract

AetherGeo is a standalone piece of software (current version 1.0) that aims to enable the user to analyze raster data, with a special focus on processing multi- and hyperspectral images. Being developed in Python 3.12.4, this application is a free, open-source alternative for spectral analysis, something considered beneficial for researchers, allowing for a flexible approach to start working on the topic without acquiring proprietary software licenses. It provides the user with a set of tools for spectral data analysis through classical approaches, such as band ratios and RGB combinations, but also more elaborate techniques, such as endmember extraction and unsupervised image classification with partial spectral unmixing techniques. While it has been tested on visible and near-infrared (VNIR), short-wave infrared (SWIR), and VNIR-SWIR datasets, the functions implemented have the potential to be applied to other spectral ranges. On top of this, all results can be visualized within the software, and some tools allow for the inspection and comparison of spectra and spectral libraries. Providing software with these capabilities in a unified platform has the potential to positively impact research and education, as students and educators usually have limited access to proprietary software.

Keywords: hyperspectral imaging; target identification; image classification; dimensionality reduction; endmember extraction; spectral analysis

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1. Introduction

Using data that describe variations in how each given material interacts with light across different wavelengths is a common technique for characterizing materials at any scale [1,2]. Thus, optical remote sensing centers around acquiring variations in how the surface material interacts with the light from the sun. Machine learning (ML) algorithms are typically applied to process such remote sensing data due to the high quantity of data, and this is a topic that has experienced exponential growth in the last few years [3].

Multiple sensors onboard different satellites are available for data acquisition by academic and non-academic communities, either multispectral or hyperspectral [3], and remote sensing techniques have shown great potential in identifying variations in materials present in the ground, therefore having extensive potential for geological applications [4,5]. One of the main current problems is the limited access potential users have to tools that enable efficient processing and analysis of such data in free, all-in-one software. For this reason, building a tool focused on geological applications and data analysis seems to meet the demand for specific applications that are free and open-source [6].

In recent years, a limited number of software programs have been developed to provide possible users access to such tools, especially outside the scope of proprietary packages such as “Environment for Visualizing Images” (ENVI) [7]. Some alternatives have recently been proposed [8–11]. We believe that such projects are a step toward giving research and educational communities access to free open-access software.

HypeRvieW [8] is a license-free software that runs on the Linux operating system. While it is developed using the C language, it provides great capabilities for spatial-spectral supervised classification. Another important feature is the integrated 2D noise correction function, which uses wavelets and soft-thresholding [12]. Its main limitation is the lack of compatibility with more common file types for remote sensing optical images from satellite missions.

HypPy [9] provides a different range of tools, focusing on taking advantage of the physical meaning of the wavelength values in place of band numbers. Another advantage is compatibility with all default ENVI file formats. While not focused on typical endmember extraction, it can perform mapping based on variations in central wavelength position and relative depth, making it a valuable tool for spectral analysis.

HYPER-Tools [10] is a MATLAB-based [13] interface that provides extensive tools for the preprocessing and analysis of spectral data. For the second component, the functions range from dimensionality reduction, endmember identification, clustering, and classification. The main limitation is the dependency on proprietary software.

EnMap-box [11] is a plugin for QGIS that provides an extensive set of tools for hyperspectral and multispectral image analysis in a Geographic Information System (GIS) environment. One of the main advantages is the time series visualization function. Though developed to focus on spectral analysis in a broader sense, it also provides some specific tools for geological applications across multiple fields of study. One of the main contributions of AetherGeo is providing a 3D interactive point cloud tool for endmember selection.

Considering some of the limitations identified in other free alternatives, we propose a new software, AetherGeo, with similar capabilities to the mentioned tools but with significant new functions: (i) a higher number of tools/algorithms for dimensionality reduction, (ii) density-based clustering algorithms for classification, and (iii) 3D point cloud selection for endmember extraction. Additionally, AetherGeo is not limited by proprietary components in any of its functionalities, making it a pertinent contribution to the current state-of-the-art technology. A more detailed comparison with other alternatives can be found in Appendix A.

This work aims to present the AetherGeo software, its interface, main components, and functionalities, while showcasing some processing workflows that can be achieved entirely within the software. The current state of the software allows for the use of classical remote sensing capabilities, such as dimensionality reduction algorithms [14], band ratios [15], clustering [16], and endmember extraction and classification [17]. The last-mentioned techniques have shown extensive potential across multiple geological applications [18,19]. Additionally, AetherGeo serves as a tool for testing and implementing advanced analysis algorithms in the future and, no less importantly, implementing preprocessing algorithms essential for addressing the range ambiguity and noise associated with sensor data [20–22].

Overall, this free, open-source software can serve as an alternative to proprietary software for dimensionality reduction, endmember extraction, spectral analysis, and image classification of multi- and hyperspectral data, with a special focus on (but not limited to) geological applications. The user-friendly interface (GUI) allows it to reach a broader audience with ready-to-use tools and no programming knowledge required. Additionally, the software can be installed on Windows via an executable installer (<https://www.fc.up.pt/RS-GISLab/aethergeo.html>, accessed on 23 May 2025). As for users with more

programming experience, since the program is open source, there is the opportunity to use the functions provided in independent programs/workflows or make alterations to those functions based on user-specific needs.

2. Spectral Data Analysis

“Light” is commonly used to describe the visible component of the electromagnetic spectrum, but in reality, optical data acquired with sensors can span more than the visible component, something important for the characterization of materials and commonly used for the differentiation of minerals in geological applications (Figure 1) [23].

This ability to characterize materials is associated with light’s interactions with materials, which vary based on their chemical and physical properties. For this reason, the use of optical data for characterization via remote sensing is a topic that has been used for a long time in multiple domains of study, especially those related to remote sensing [2,24,25]. The launch of the Hyperion-01 sensor [26] marked a significant advancement in the application of hyperspectral data for different fields of study, with a special emphasis on environmental and geological applications [5,27]. Recent advancements in sensor technology, noise levels, and the launch of new satellites due to “Precursore IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa” (PRISMA) and “Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program” (EnMap) missions not only provide easier access to quality data but also incentivize the need to take full advantage of these data, which have a lot of potential but require more detailed processing due to their high complexity.

Figure 1. (a) Almandine mineral. (b) Respective infrared spectrum [28].

It is also important to introduce the difference between multispectral and hyperspectral data (Figure 2). The first one is better described as each pixel having a discrete set of associated variables (based on the number of bands), while in the other case, the bands are narrow (2–10 nanometers), and therefore, there is a large number of bands covering the zone of the electromagnetic spectrum being measured [29,30].

This continuous property of the spectra associated with hyperspectral data makes them a powerful tool for earth surface characterization [31], and therefore, they have significant potential for geological applications. The capacity for academic and non-academic communities to have access to such data covering extensive areas has been greatly improved by the recent PRISMA and EnMap, with the added benefit of these products being commonly provided with level 2A and, therefore, having already been corrected for atmospheric effects, making integration with the rest of the analysis workflows faster and easier.

Additionally, access to hyperspectral satellite data is expected to increase in the future due to new missions such as the Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission for the Environment (CHIME) by the European Space Agency (ESA), which consists of two satellites (CHIME-A and CHIME-B) providing systematic hyperspectral data [32].

Figure 2. Comparison of multispectral and hyperspectral imaging [33].

Though sensors onboard unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), aircraft, and spacecraft can acquire such images, access to proper techniques for processing and inspecting such data is essential for retrieving significant information. Traditional techniques, such as false color RGB combinations, allow for fast, somewhat intuitive evaluation of the overall scenery but lack concrete interpretability of results and capabilities to consider more than three bands.

It is also common to use unsupervised learning algorithms when analyzing spectral data since they provide data-driven results that uncover complex links in data [34] without requiring labeled data. The most commonly used unsupervised approaches for analyzing remote sensing optical data are clustering and dimensionality reduction algorithms, the latter being especially important for hyperspectral data due to what is described in the literature as the curse of dimensionality [35].

Another alternative is spectral unmixing, especially algorithms under the category of partial spectral unmixing, since they do not rely on having the full information for each component present in the image [36], something unreasonable for most geological applications. These algorithms focus on classifying each pixel of an image based on the likelihood of a given input spectrum being present.

There are two approaches for selecting the input spectra for spectral unmixing. The first consists of importing the spectra from an already existing spectral library [28]. The second relies on finding spectrally pure pixels within the image. Retrieving these pure independent components, commonly called endmembers, from the image itself has the advantage that the spectrum being assumed as a pure material in the image is already adjusted for variations in material composition, sensor noise, and spectral shifts, in this way overcoming typical limitations associated with this type of analysis [37]. The software AetherGeo allows the user to undertake both approaches.

3. Software Introduction

The current version (v1.0) of the software allows the user to analyze data in the form of an image. This is done with a focus on the analysis of spectral data (multi- and hyperspectral). Handling the high-dimensional datasets associated with these data is challenging, but the user must have access to adequate analysis and visualization tools. For this reason, the software visualization approach is pixel-based but saves the geospatial metadata of the original file to any output file. This allows for interoperability with GIS software.

Regarding image visualization, after importing a raster file (Figure 3A), the user can also change the bands displayed as an RGB combination (Figure 3C), a common tool for inspecting spectral data [38,39].

Figure 3. AetherGeo's main interface. (A) Input and layer selection. (B) Icon bar functions. (C) Display settings (C1)—RGB combination selector; (C2)—Image adjustment. (D) Main data processing functions.

Continuing with this approach, the icon bar (Figure 3B) in the top part, for now, has a total of three functions. The first one allows the user to generate a two-dimensional plot showing the relationship between components of the data, allowing for selection and visualization of the selected pixels. The second and third functions allow the user to access the user guide and license, respectively, which can be accessed by clicking the respective icons (Figure 4a,b) on the software.

Figure 4. (a) Help button, for opening the user guide. (b) License button.

On the right side of the screen is a toolbar for accessing the different available data processing tools (Figure 3D).

To achieve all the functionalities, the Python language [40] was used in conjunction with different packages, such as Matplotlib 3.5.0 [41], NumPy 1.23.0 [42], Raste-

rio 1.2.0 [43], Spectral 0.22.1 [44], scikit-learn 1.0.0 [45], Umap 0.5.0 [46], SciPy 1.7.0 [47], scikit-image 0.19.0 [48], h5py 3.6.0 [49], pyproj 3.3.0 [50], OpenGL 3.1.5 [51], and PyQt6 6.4.0 [52].

The current version supports TIF, DAT, and HE5 files for image inputs. As for spectral libraries, it currently supports SLI and (.txt) files. All outputs are saved as TIF files.

4. Related Software Tools

This section focuses on the different tools currently available and is subdivided in the same order as those categories displayed in the software. Table 1 comprises the different functions available in the current state of the software. More in-depth explanations for most function groups can be found in their respective subsections.

Table 1. Software’s main functions.

Function Group	Function	Description	Input
Icon Bar	2D Plot	Select points from the image based on the associated information	Image
	User Guide	Opens the user manual	---
	License	Opens the license description	---
Preprocessing	Normalize data	[0, 1] pixel-wise normalization	Image
	Attribute Wavelengths	Add wavelength metadata to the image	Image + Select Satellite
Dimensionality Reduction	Principal Component Analysis [53]	Reduce the amount of data while maintaining the most significant or independent features.	Image Mask (optional) Number of components to be kept
	Independent Component Analysis [54]		
	Non-Negative Matrix Factorization [55]		
Endmember Extraction	Pixel Purity Index	Identify the most extreme pixels in a given image	Image Mask (optional) Number of projections
	Generate Point Cloud	Generates a 3D embedding of the data from where the user can extract endmembers	Image Mask (PPI)
Spectral Unmixing	Spectral Angle Mapper [56]	Attributes a value to each pixel based on the angular distance between the pixel spectra and the given input spectra	Image Input spectra
Clustering	K-Means [57]	Performs clustering based on distance from the cluster centroid	Image Mask (optional) Number of classes
	Ordering Points to Identify Cluster Structure [58]	Performs clustering based on varying density zones	Image Mask (optional) Minimum samples X_i Minimum cluster size
	Mean Spectra from Cluster	Saves a spectral library based on the mean spectra for each cluster from previous functions	Image Clustering results
Spectral Libraries	Import Library	Enables the user to import spectral libraries	File path
	Spectra Analyst	Visualization tool for spectral libraries, their components, and respective analysis	---
Others	Band Ratios	Perform calculations based on pixel values for input bands	Image

4.1. Preprocessing

This category currently has two different functions. The first enables the user to generate a layer composed of a normalized version of the input data. This normalization is conducted through a process that sets the lowest value to 0 and scales the other bands

proportionally so that the highest possible value is 1, thus normalizing the vector of band values associated with each pixel [59]. This process is important for minimizing the effects of light intensity changes across the scene and maximizing the focus on the structure of the spectrum itself.

The second function enables the user to attribute the wavelength metadata to an image if that given image lacks previous wavelength metadata and the number of bands associated with it is the same as the number of bands for the selected sensor. This attribution is important for later stages to generate proper spectral libraries with correct wavelength data.

4.2. Spectral Dimensionality Reduction

The following group of functions is built around techniques for dimensionality reduction. For any of the functions under this category, the user can choose a layer to be used as input, another layer to be used as a mask (optional), and a given number of components to be present after the reduction.

Three different algorithms are implemented to achieve this task: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [53], Independent Component Analysis (ICA) [54], and Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) [55]. After running any of the functions, the user can generate a graph representing a significance value for each of the new bands. For the case of PCA, the software outputs a graph based on the explained variance ratio of each component (Figure 5); for ICA, a kurtosis value is used [54]; and a significance value, which represents how much each given feature is present across the entire dataset, based on the L2 norm of matrix W [60] is used in the case of NMF.

Figure 5. Example of PCA explained variance ratio graph for seven components.

The first two described functions are already well-established in the remote sensing geological application literature [14]. On the other hand, NMF is not as established for this specific application, despite showing promising results both for dimensionality reduction [55] and endmember extraction and classification [61]. The NMF algorithm also has several advantages due to its nature of working with non-negative values (reflectance values are

always positive), as it always generates positive results, making preserving the physical meaning of the reflectance values easier. These constraints regarding potential negative values in the input dataset are also essential for achieving efficient computational times.

4.3. Band Ratios

The application of band ratios to retrieve information from spectral data has applications in all remote sensing fields, being an important feature with extensive application in the geologic context [2,15]. This function is added in a context where the user can select from the layer in a given file and a set group of basic mathematical procedures, allowing for math calculations that include sum, subtraction, multiplication, and division of different bands, generating an output file composed of a single layer. This output file can be further inspected based on value variations across the image using the 2D plot function available in the icon bar.

4.4. Spectral Library Management and Visualization

An important feature when working with hyperspectral and multispectral data is the visualization of spectral libraries (Figure 6). This is the term for files containing groups of different spectra from previous studies, such as open-access libraries resampled for different satellite sensors [62] or extracted from an image.

Figure 6. Comparison between spectra using the “Spectra Analyst” tool. The spectra displayed correspond to the selection on the left panel.

In this tool, the spectral angle mapper (SAM) algorithm [56,63] can also be used to measure the angle between two selected spectra. An angle of zero degrees means the spectra are precisely equal; as the angle increases, the spectra are less similar.

4.5. Endmember Extraction

The only currently available tool for spatial dimensionality reduction is the pixel purity index (PPI). This algorithm focuses on attributing a purity index for each pixel of a given image. This is an important step in finding the most unique pixels most likely to correspond to pure material [37]. To achieve this task, the algorithm compares each image pixel against a group of vectors (skewers) and classifies its likelihood of being pure based on a threshold set by the user [30]. After a selected number of iterations, the output is a binary layer based on whether pixels are considered pure or not.

To retrieve the pure spectra directly from the image, the “Point Cloud Extraction” function allows the user to select the desired input files and generate a three-dimensional point cloud based on Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) embedding [46].

From the pop-up window (Figure 7), the user can either run the automatic selection of the Ordering Points to Identify Cluster Structure (OPTICS) algorithm [58] to perform density-based clustering (see Section 4.7) or manually select multiple regions in the point cloud, forming clusters to extract their representative spectra. With this workflow, the user can inspect each endmember spectrum and save the results as a spectral library for future use.

Figure 7. (a) Instruction menu for endmember extraction. (b) Point cloud selection (purple color represents the points selected as endmember). (c) Visualization of the respective selected endmember spectra.

4.6. SAM

Currently, SAM is the only algorithm available for classification based on specific spectral inputs. Considering a given layer (corresponding with raster spectral data) and a spectrum corresponding to a given endmember, the SAM algorithm attributes a value to each pixel based on the similarity between the pixel and the input spectrum. It is assumed that a higher similarity between both spectra indicates a higher likelihood of the endmember material being present. The SAM algorithm is described in Equation (1) [63]:

$$\angle(x, y) = \arccos \frac{x \cdot y}{\|x\| \|y\|} \quad (1)$$

where x and y are vectors composed of $[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$ and $[y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n]$, respectively, and represent the array of reflectance values associated with a given pixel and the array of reflectance values associated with a given endmember.

The usage of this algorithm for geological applications is common due to the reliability around light and angle deviations across the landscape [27,64].

The endmember used as input can be a spectrum from a spectral library, such as the United States Geological Survey (USGS) open-access library [28]. Another alternative is to generate a spectral library composed of the pure components present in a given image. This approach shows promising results since it is robust against sensor noise and deviations of the spectra [37].

A typical workflow for classification after endmember extraction can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Workflow for classification using endmember extraction and spectral unmixing.

The spectral dimensionality reduction step is not mandatory but is highly recommended, especially for hyperspectral data, due to what is known in the literature as the curse of dimensionality [35].

Appendix B provides a practical example of this workflow with more optional steps regarding preprocessing and final data inspection. It shows how to use multiple functions to achieve classification based on an endmember extracted from the image, while starting only with a satellite image product without previous information or processing.

4.7. Clustering

Another implemented alternative is to use unsupervised classification clustering techniques [65] to classify a given image. To achieve this task, OPTICS [58] was the main algorithm selected for clustering due to its similarity with density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise (DBSCAN) [66]. DBSCAN has been proven useful for analyzing geological [67] and spectral data [68]. However, OPTICS has the advantage of having a higher degree of interpretation due to having fewer parameters set by the user [69], with the main ones being the “Minimum samples”, which refers to the minimum number of points in a neighborhood for a point to be considered a core point, and “Xi”, a parameter that controls the model’s sensitivity to changes in point density, therefore affecting cluster boundaries.

K-means clustering is also implemented in AetherGeo in the form of k-means++ [57]. Due to this algorithm’s fast processing of extensive datasets, K-means is ideal for processing remote sensing data, providing the user with clustering results that segment the data into classes with a higher degree of similarity.

It is also important to mention that the last available function, “Retrieve spectrum from cluster”, allows the user to extract the mean spectrum for each cluster generated by the previously selected clustering algorithm. Thus, this function allows for a more detailed interpretation, especially when used in conjunction with the “Spectral library management and visualization” class. Figure 9 gives an example result from clustering with K-means.

Figure 9. (a) Parameter and layer selection menu. (b) Clustering results before saving the image.

5. Discussion

The current version of AetherGeo is mainly intended to work with geospatial data, but the visualization is pixel-based and not georeferenced. For the results generated by any analysis to have spatial meaning, all necessary metadata for georeferentiation is saved in conjunction with any new layer created. Therefore, all the output images generated by AetherGeo can be later analyzed in a GIS environment.

Compared with other alternatives, especially other free, open-source projects [8–11], it is important to highlight that AetherGeo provides the user with extensive tools for endmember extraction from a 3D point cloud, something that the other free software alternatives described do not offer. Other contributions of AetherGeo for state-of-the-art geological applications are as follows: (i) AetherGeo offers per-band significance graphs for each dimensionality reduction technique; (ii) it is one of the few software that offers the NMF algorithm for dimensionality reduction, having potential for geological application; (iii) AetherGeo is the only software that allows intuitive and interactive 3D point cloud extraction with embedding resulting from UMAP, which provides great capabilities to preserve local and global data structure [46]; (iv) it provides density-based clustering for image classification and endmember extraction; (v) AetherGeo offers a 2D plot function that enables the user to select pixels based on their associated values.

Figure A1 of Appendix B shows a more detailed workflow using multiple functions to achieve image classification based on an endmember extracted from a given image and only using such an image as a starting point (without previous information), highlighting how multiple functions can be used together to achieve a final classification result, and also serves as a guide for anyone learning how to use the software.

Additionally, all the tools in AetherGeo are provided without any dependency on proprietary packages or software, and the user can modify any of its components without

any proprietary license. In this way, it differs from an available alternative [10] that runs on MATLAB, which requires a full license. AetherGeo, built in Python, provides access to state-of-the-art libraries, especially for machine learning.

Though the current version does not include any specific algorithm for noise correction, we intend to explore some alternatives currently present in the literature [20–22] in the future and subsequently add some functions to the preprocessing group regarding such matters.

Regarding the potential for geological applications, the capabilities of AetherGeo software can be expanded to include more than satellite data, such as UAV, airborne, and laboratory data. Since the software is developed to extract information from images, the scale of work is defined by the capabilities to acquire corrected images, which, in the case of particular sensors for UAV, airborne, and laboratory applications, may require specific preprocessing with software developed for the specific sensor. Even though the image analysis functions were tested in images containing data from the “visible and near-infrared” (VNIR) and “short-wave infrared” (SWIR), they can also be tested and applied to other spectral ranges. Due to the flexibility of working with different spectral ranges and image scales, we believe this software provides helpful analysis tools across different geological applications. Additionally, since hyperspectral data can be helpful in many areas of expertise, the hyperspectral image analysis features available in AetherGeo can be explored by specialists in other fields of study.

Another topic that has been discussed extensively in the literature is that even though many algorithms have been developed, they tend to be difficult to test due to either limitations in testing data or limitations in access and applicability by other experts. For this reason, building an intuitive layout in the form of a GUI (Graphical User Interface) enables experts from different areas to have access to multiple functionalities and algorithms without requiring extensive programming knowledge or other complications.

In addition to improving accessibility, the software also contributes to facilitating reproducibility and consistency in research by providing a standardized environment where procedures can be executed with predefined parameters and settings. This strengthens scientific rigor and also promotes collaboration and transparency.

6. Conclusions

Software that focuses on the analysis of image spectroscopy remote sensing data has been of limited access to the academic and non-academic communities. With this in mind, AetherGeo was built to allow the community access to multiple remote sensing techniques inside a single free, open-source piece of software.

By providing a set of tools and functions in an all-in-one environment with visualization capabilities, AetherGeo can provide a great user experience while also supporting some of the most common data file types currently in use. Compatibility with more file types is expected in future versions. This approach also provides an infrastructure for testing and implementation of new state-of-the-art algorithms in the future.

The current version mainly provides capabilities for classic image analysis tools and endmember extraction. Future versions can extend this by providing new functionalities, improving current visualization options, and supporting more file types. In this way, we believe AetherGeo can continue providing the community access to state-of-the-art techniques for geological applications, which is something of interest to both professionals and students.

In the future, functionalities related to data integration and the development of predictive maps will be implemented under the same scope and workflow format, since this tool

is mainly provided as software developed for geological applications and data analysis. Other spectral unmixing algorithms could also be added in future software versions.

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Data Availability Statement: The source code for the software can be found at <https://github.com/EarthObservation/S34I> (accessed on 17 May 2025). The software can be installed on Windows via an executable installer (<https://www.fc.up.pt/RS-GISLab/aethergeo.html>, accessed on 23 May 2025).

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

DBSCAN	Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise
EnMap	Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program
ENVI	Environment for Visualizing Images
GIS	Geographic Information System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ICA	Independent Component Analysis
IDL	Interactive Data Language
ML	Machine Learning
MATLAB	Matrix Laboratory
NMF	Non-negative Matrix Factorization
OPTICS	Ordering Points to Identify Cluster Structure
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PPI	Pixel Purity Index
PRISMA	Precursore IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa
SAM	Spectral Angle Mapper
SWIR	Short-Wave Infrared
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UMAP	Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection
USGS	United States Geological Survey
VNIR	Visible and Near-Infrared

Appendix A

This section presents Table A1, which is composed of a comparison between AetherGeo and the open-source alternatives discussed in the introduction and discussion sections.

Table A1. Comparison between AetherGeo v1.0, AetherGeo v1.1, and other open-source alternatives

	File Type Support (for Images)	Requires Proprietary License	Visualize and Inspect Spectra from Spectral Libraries	3D Endmember Extraction	Expert-Based Algorithms for Mineral Identification	Noise Correction Functions
HypeRvieW [8]	Raw, MAT, HRW	No	No	No	No	Yes
HypPy [9]	DAT	No	Yes	No	No	No
HYPER-Tools [10]	MAT, TIF, and DAT	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes
EnMap-Box [11]	TIF, DAT, and HE5	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
AetherGeo v1.0	TIF, DAT, and HE5	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
AetherGeo v1.1	MAT and other new state-of-the-art file types	No	Yes	Yes	Possibly	Yes

Appendix B

Figure A1 shows a step-by-step example for identifying an endmember in an area of interest in a given image and performing classification. It proceeds as follows: First, import the image. The second step is optional and depends on previous information, but it is recommended that normalization be performed and the correct wavelengths be attributed to each band. As a third step, run one of the clustering algorithms; in the example case, K-means was used with seven classes (Figure A1A; partially shown in Figure 9). Follow this by inspecting the results. In this case, classes 1 and 6 coincide with our zones of interest. Proceed by generating a mask based on classes that match our zones of interest (selection in QGIS). To identify the pixels most likely to be pure, perform PPI with the original image and mask from the last step. Follow this by using PPI results and the original image in the “Generate Point Cloud” function, and select the extreme points in the cloud (Figure A1B; partially shown in Figure 7). After selection, inspect the spectra and save the results as a spectral library (Figure A1C; partially shown in Figure 7). To perform classification, start by importing the spectral library from the last step and performing SAM with the original image and the desired endmember from the library. To finalize the classification, use the 2D plot feature to extract results with the desired value (for SAM, a smaller angle means the best results; Figure A1D). Finish by saving and inspecting the final results (Figure A1E).

Figure A1. Example workflow for image classification. (A): K-means results with seven classes; (B): selection of the extreme points (endmembers in purple color) in the 3D point cloud; (C): spectral library of selected endmembers; (D): 2D plot feature to extract SAM results with a smaller angle (red); (E): final results with target areas in red.

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Attachment C – Geological map at 1:50 000 scale

Figure 70. Crustal Structure of the Iberian Variscides (Simancas et al., 2013).

Attachment D – Additional results

Figure 71. K-means results.

Figure 72. A) EnMap Image; B) PCA component with high noise. C) PCA component with high values related to vegetation; ICA component strongly correlated with outcrops.

Figure 73. Confusion matrices. A) XGBoost; B) CatBoost; C) RF; D) MLP; E) SVM.